

TEA

The
European Archaeologist

The newsletter of EAA members for EAA members
Issue 80 – Spring 2024

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Cover

A Bronze sword, erosion and heights

Malene R. Beck

Museums of Eastern Funen

Being uncomfortable with moving heights, the investigation of a Bronze Age barrow threatened by erosion, definitely brought me out of my comfort zone.

The round barrow is situated in the beautiful countryside on the east coast of Northeast Funen (Hindsholm), Denmark. Hovering on a brink 12 meters above sea level it is highly exposed to erosion caused by wind, rain and sea – and even more so in the future because of climate changes. The remaining parts of the monument will presumably disappear into the sea before the end of this century.

In 2015 pieces of a bronze sword was found on the beach below the barrow. This instigated a more thorough investigation and registration of the monument in 2016. The investigation was financially supported by the Danish Agency for Culture and Palaces as part of their focus on the increasing number of scheduled sites and monuments threatened by erosion. Because the barrow was scheduled, we decided not to excavate and thereby destroy the remaining part, as it still holds a prominent and very visible position in the surrounding agricultural and coastal landscape. Instead, we took advantage of the possibilities the erosion had left us. By 2016 approximately half of the barrow had disappeared into the sea, and this in fact created a natural profile right through the center of it. Based on the results from recent excavations of a large bronze age barrow showing complex building sequences (the Skelhøj Project) our aim was to establish, how this more regular sized barrow of 20-22 meters in diameter was constructed, and to recreate the Bronze Age landscape using pollen and macrofossil analyses.

The picture shows me in the limited space of the lift basket, cleaning the barrow profile. I prefer being on firm ground, so the trip up in the lift, as well as the cleaning task, making the lift move up and down 12 to 16 meters above ground, was definitely challenging. We cleaned the profile in two-meter broad sections and made photogrammetric registration before moving the lift repeatedly. This enabled us to register the entire barrow profile, showing at least three burial phases and demonstrating the use of wet turfs and turfs from areas that had already been de-turfed once. Leaving the comfort zone brought new perspectives on bronze age barrow construction – but please don't ask me to go up there again!

Letter from the Editors

Dear Colleagues,

Do you know the origins of the phrase “context is king”? Many of us have heard it used in archaeological settings and may have mentally filed it under a collection of archaeological truisms alongside “the dead do not bury themselves” and “it is always the end of a dig, that the most exciting finds emerge”. Apparently, although people variously credit either Viacom founder Sumner Redstone or Microsoft CEO Bill Gates with having first crowned context, the phrase was in fact coined in 1974 in an article by Click and Baird in *Magazine Editing and Production* on selecting the ideal spread for the glossies ([Karbasfrooshan 2020](#)). However, when archaeologists talk about the supremacy of context, we mean it to encompass multiple packages of reality. Of course, we speak of the importance of context as physical location within a site, but we also talk of ‘context’ in terms of relationality.

As a young archaeologist on her first excavation many years ago in the courtyard of a medieval castle in Cēsis, Latvia one of us (Reiter) very distinctly remembers being delighted at uncovering a portion of a small clay pipe. Her trench companions—who were fellow British archaeology students far more experienced than she at the time—shrugged off her find and advised her to pop it into our surface finds lot. It was only later on when the excavation director had worked his way over to them that they found out just how special tobacco equipment actually was for the period in question within a Latvian setting. While in Britain, such a find would be commonplace (that is, within a different context), in its Latvian context the find was actually more important.

It behoves us to remember that many of the greatest archaeological finds that garner the most ardent public interest were at first discarded, lost or ignored when they entered the record. As Tony Robinson and Mick Aston claimed in their delightfully tongue-in-cheek book (2003), archaeology literally *is* rubbish! Indeed, one man’s trash is another man’s treasure. In many cases, it is just a matter of context.

Nevertheless, context also has a more pervasive and less-immediately apparent effect. We are all formed by our national, cultural, political and linguistic backgrounds to think in certain ways. That thinking shapes our research both in terms of the questions we ask and in the ways that results are interpreted. For both of us, reading Wilk (1985) on the ‘The Ancient Maya and the Political Present’ was an ‘Aha!’ moment in our academic lives. In that paper, Wilk showed that researchers essentially find in the past a mirror of the political and socioeconomic circumstances that they themselves experience in the present. While archaeologists may not say that our own individual contexts are ‘king’ in this instance, they do seem to dictate our behaviour to a certain degree.

Part of our remit within *TEA* is to put those behaviours and the contexts in which they play out into perspective. *TEA* is also intended to be a reflection of the times and the context in which current research is conducted. In light of that, we include in this issue the recent [EAA Statement](#) condemning the loss of life and cultural heritage due to the Gaza crisis for your reference. Focal points on the European level include a presentation of opportunities to apply for support of scientific research with the [E-RIHS platform](#), a discussion of the [EU Benchmarks](#) as a means of gauging past and present political developments relative to heritage and a brief report on the [spring CINGO meeting](#).

In terms of research overviews and hot topics, once again we have a wide spread of material within this issue. These include articles on [preserving heritage in wartime Ukraine](#) as well as the current campaign to [protect the rock art in Vingen, Norway](#). Other contributions present a fascinating example of a [rare early copper mould from Italy](#) and an overview of the long-standing traditions [of chalking the Uffington White Horse](#) in Britain. A final project overview of the [Grave Goods project](#) based in the UK is both food for thought as well as comparative context for other studies elsewhere.

Of common thematic interest are our usual highpoints: the [EAA Calendar](#), [In Case You Missed It](#) and two interviews over *TEA*. The first interview is with EAA Member and Polish national now living in London [Robert Staniuk](#). The second is with EAA Official [Zena Kamash](#), who is part of the European Journal of Archaeology publication staff. We are also delighted to announce that we have not one, but two EAA Communities to present in this issue: the [Community for Archaeology and Tourism](#) and [COMFORT](#), a group focused on the study of fortifications. Two additional contributions offer the results of a [recent survey and workshop on life/work balance for women working in archaeology and palaeoecology](#) and a [review of the recent Current Archaeology LIVE! awards](#), which took place at UCL back in February. Once again, we are delighted to announce *TEA*'s latest [photojournalism competition](#). Please see our [Announcements](#) section for further details. If you need inspiration, you need go no further than Malene R. Beck's winning photo, which is featured on this issue's [cover](#)—Beck's image definitely puts working outside the comfort zone in context!

We must end this issue on a sad note. We recently lost a cornerstone of modern archaeological theory; [Chris Tilley](#) is memorialized here by Michael Rowlands of UCL and Kristian Kristiansen of Gothenburg University.

Today, we are all faced with a continual panoply of news, ranging from the loss of an influential thinker and colleague to the collapse of the Key Bridge in Baltimore, USA and from ecological disasters in Denmark to the crisis in Gaza. As previously, there is a lot of fake news these days, and there is even more news that is presented in a heavily partisan manner. As archaeologists, we are in a unique position to understand how objects as well as actions, events and political approaches can seem vastly different depending upon how, when and where the decisions are taken and how, when and where those decisions are presented. In a world where differences of opinion are too often 'fighting words', archaeology can provide a voice of reason. After all, a big part of what archaeologists do is to cross barriers of time and space in order to uncover what links people together—what makes us who we are. This spring, we urge each of you to take those principles out of their archaeological context and apply them to the living world as well. Together, we can add context where it is so sorely needed.

Best Regards,

Samantha S. Reiter and Matthew J. Walsh

Editors

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Calendar for EAA Members

Calendar for EAA members April – August 2024

25 April	Registration and membership payment deadline for presenters (first authors)
25 April	Deadline for Annual Meeting registration cancellation without cancellation fee
April – May	Call for nominations to the EAA Student Award circulated to the Members
1 May	Deadline for nominations to the European Heritage Prize
6 May	Announcement of acceptance / rejection of poster proposals
6 May	76th EAA management meeting
13 May	97 th EAA Executive Board meeting
17 May	Preliminary version of scientific programme announced at the 30 th EAA Annual Meeting website
31 May	Deadline for membership and Annual Meeting registration fee payment for presenters (first authors) of posters
31 May	Deadline for last cancellation of excursions (no refund after this date)
11 July	Deadline for last Annual Meeting registration cancellation incl. cancellation of paid social events and other booked items (no refund after this date)
31 July (latest)	EAA Secretariat sends out ballot papers to current Members
1 August	EAA Student Award submissions deadline
1 August	TEA photojournalism competition submission deadline
15 August (latest)	EAA Secretariat sends AMBM Report to current Members
30 August	12:00 CEST (noon) deadline for submitting votes in EAA election
28 - 31 August 2024	EAA 2024 Annual Meeting in Rome

EAA Statement

Statement on Threats to Archaeology and Archaeologists Arising from the Israel/Gaza Crisis

The European Association of Archaeologists is the largest membership organisation of archaeologists in Europe and is committed to the promotion and protection of cultural heritage. We are concerned at the effects on cultural heritage and our archaeological colleagues of events in the Middle East arising from the current Israel/ Gaza crisis. We have deep concerns and compassion for the unbearable human suffering and call on all parties involved in the conflict to strive for immediate solutions that safeguard human lives, and the cultural heritage on the region.

We have a commitment to the holistic preservation of the integrity, authenticity and diversity of the rich cultural heritage that is located in the region and which is the expression of a multicultural and multireligious past and present of this region. We therefore deplore and condemn any act of damage, destruction or distortion of cultural heritage sites, including relevant museums and archives, which has happened because of a conflict or of the lack of respect for any of the cultures that have flourished in the region. The EAA is also committed to keep a vigilant eye on the removal and circulation of cultural objects, which are stolen or illegally exported from their archaeological, cultural context or museum/archive collection amidst the current state of armed conflict in the region, in line with the UNESCO Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export, and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property ([1970](#)) and the UNIDROIT Convention on Stolen and Illegally Exported Cultural Objects ([1995](#)).

We call upon all parties to such conflicts – whether directly involved or acting in support of combatants – to consider, among their concerns, the implementation of appropriate strategies to safeguard the cultural heritages of the region. We implore them to adhere to the Hague Conventions on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict ([1954](#)) and its First (1954) and Second Protocols (1999) and other relevant materials and rules. It is crucial that armed operations avoid targeting archaeological and cultural heritage sites, and maintain a safe distance from their immediate surroundings.

We have an additional concern for the safety of, and effects of the conflict on, our colleagues in the region, regardless of citizenship, ethnicity, religion or political or other allegiance, and the communities with which they work.

As archaeologists, we wish to emphasize, in the strongest terms possible, that cultural heritage is a fundamental pillar for the existence, identity and well-being of human societies – not only as material relics, but also as witnesses of the past. The maintenance of cultural heritage is therefore an irreplaceable component of basic human rights. Out of respect for human life and the shared history that binds us all together, regardless of religion or nationality, the EAA strongly urges that all acts of war and violence must cease immediately.

In Case You Missed It...

Joana Valdez-Tullett

EAA Social Media Editor

[Scientists uncover evidence that microplastics are contaminating archaeological remains](#)

[Human Brains found at archaeological sites are surprisingly well-preserved](#)

[Archaeologists unearth carved bone containing medicinal herbs in Roman-period settlement](#)

[11,000-year-old stone ornaments indicate early body perforation](#)

['Landmark paper' shows why ice age European wore jewellery](#)

[Tooth analysis reveals Roman child travelled thousands of miles to Britain](#)

[A 2700 year old temple discovered on Greek Island of Evia](#)

[#SaveVingen](#) and [Vingen Rock Art in Norway](#)

[Archaeology of the Roman Conquest](#)

[PEPAdb \(Prehistoric Europe's Personal Adornment database\)](#)

[The ancient history of 'forgotten crops'](#)

All images used in "In Case You Missed It" are from FlatIcon (www.flaticon.com)

Notice

The upcoming European Elections and EAA's Benchmarks for Archaeology and Heritage Protection

Sophie Hüglin and Jean-Olivier Gransard-Desmond

Co-Chairs of the EAA Political Strategies Community

Between 6-9 June 2024, a new European Parliament will be elected. EU citizens can vote in their country of origin, from abroad or in the EU country in which they reside. Check whether you can vote and where you might have to register [here](#). Be sure to do this in good time, as registration deadlines vary from one country to another.

A group of EAA Communities has set up [Benchmarks for Archaeology and Heritage Protection 2024-2029](#). On the European level, the following five pressing topics have been identified:

- 1) Addressing climate change challenges for cultural heritage;
- 2) Protecting the historic environment in planning;
- 3) Addressing the trade in archaeological material;
- 4) Facilitating the mobility of labour across borders;
- 5) Free use of images related to cultural heritage.

These Benchmarks have been sent to the seven political groups running in the EU elections and to political parties on the national level. Answers are coming in, are being continuously published and will be evaluated. Please continue watching this space these ongoing developments [here](#), the dedicated EAA benchmark space.

Some national NGOs have their own webspace where they promote the EAA campaign; in France this is [ArkéoTopia](#) and in Germany [DGUF](#). The election benchmarks are also being implemented in Austria, Belgium, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Portugal and Spain. If your country is not listed above, you can have a look at the answers from parties in the same [political group](#). This will give you information on the responsiveness, the level of competency and the position of the respective political groups and the parties on a national level.

This is the second time that the EAA has undertaken the Benchmark campaign. The previous Benchmarks (2019-2024) and the respective evaluation report are available [here](#). The repetition of the project enables interested parties to check whether politicians deliver on the promises they made before the elections, and to remind them to act upon those promises once they are elected.

Notice

“Climbing the (Reykjavik) Summit together” – Gerhard Ermischer re-elected as President of the Conference of INGOs

Sophie Hüglin

EAA Commissioner to the Conference of INGOs to the Council of Europe

The President with the newly elected Standing Committee at the CINGO Spring Session in Strasbourg (France). Image with permission from the Secretariat of the Conference of INGOs

From 8-10 April 2024, the Conference of the INGOs (CINGO) at the Council of Europe in Strasbourg (CoE) held its [Spring Session](#). The whole Board had to be elected, and new Thematic Committees to be formed. One of the central tasks of the CINGO in the coming three years will be to formulate with the CoE binding statements that substantiate the protection of the environment as a human right. While EAA can offer expertise in archaeology, heritage management or the historic landscape, in order to be able to contribute it will have to cooperate closely with INGOs focusing on related topics such as nature protection, architecture, planning, culture, education and health.

On the first day, [Michael O’Flaherty](#) the newly elected Commissioner for Human Rights at the Council of Europe honoured the CINGO convention by paying it one of his first visits on the job, addressing the assembly and engaging in a Q&A session on upcoming opportunities of cooperation with civil society as represented by INGO.

Archaeologist Gerhard Ermischer, who has been CINGO President in the last three years, gave an account of his first term in office. This was overshadowed by the pandemic and the exclusion of Russia from the CoE after its invasion into Ukraine. Against this the [4th Summit of the Heads of State and Government](#) of the CoE in Iceland set a clear sign of hope with its [Reykjavík Declaration](#). In this document – especially in Appendix V – the environment plays a central role. It affirms for the first time “that a clean, healthy and sustainable environment is integral to the full enjoyment of human rights by present and future generations”. Gerhard Ermischer stressed the role that civil society can play in implementing this declaration through the CINGO at the CoE.

On the second day, the whole CINGO Board was up for [election](#). [President Gerhard Ermischer](#) himself was uncontested and affirmed in his position by a high number of votes. This enables him to continue to lead the organization with the Vice-Presidents Geneviève Laloy and Piotr Sadowski for another three years. Elected to the Standing Committee were Ruth Allen, Ece Ciftci, Ciaran John King, Simon Matthijssen, Goran Miletic, Olga Sadovskaya, Anna Sevortian and Iordanis Chorozioglou. After two full terms as Vice-President, Christoph Spreng was thanked and reminded the new Board that “the test comes now with climbing the Summit!”

During the elections, a news item came through: the [European Court of Human Rights](#) (ECHR), which is part of the CoE, just had ruled in the case Verein [Klima Seniorinnen Schweiz](#) v. Switzerland. It [admitted Switzerland’s failure to implement sufficient measures to combat climate change](#). This judgement is considered groundbreaking when it comes to the role of NGOs in urging states to protect their citizens against the consequences of climate change.

The last day was dedicated to the presentation and voting on new Thematic Committees. From the perspective of EAA the new committee on [“Inclusive Territories, Environment and Health”](#) could be an option. It is chaired by Anne Marie Chavanon and Elena Curtopassi and supported by five CINGO members and more than 20 additional CINGO organisations and experts. Its aims are formulated very wide and inclusive, reaching from the [2030 UN Sustainable Development Goals](#), [COP 16](#) (biodiversity) and [COP 29](#) (climate), the [Paris Agreement](#) and relevant CoE Conventions; it also intends to prepare normative texts on the right to a healthy environment. Until the CINGO Autumn Session it will be for EAA to evaluate with the CINGO Board whether it should join the above-mentioned Thematic Committee or whether it would be

more effective to join up with other INGOs represented at the Conference and form another committee with a focus to deliver to the implementation process of the Reykjavik Declaration.

Encouraging in this respect was Tanja Kleinsorge's presentation on the Inter-Secretariat Task Force on environment. Her job is to coordinate the different organs of the CoE – the Parliamentary Assembly (the PACE), its Court (the ECHR), the representatives at the CINGO and the over 200 conventions and enable them to push decisions resulting from the Reykjavik Declaration together. To speed up the drafting of the normative texts, her vision is to form an ad-hoc multi-disciplinary committee rather than many expert groups. She sees yesterday's ECHR ruling as a first step to put juridical pressure on states not only to have environmental "laws in the book" but also to enforce their implementation and be measured by their effectiveness.

The re-elected CINGO Board will start now to work on a new strategy paper for the coming three years. The CINGO member organisations will be able to contribute to this in several rounds. The aim is to agree on the new strategy in the CINGO Autumn Session, which will be held October 14-16, 2024. CINGO is explicitly encouraging its members to send young delegates together with their more experienced representatives to Strasbourg to make the Conference more inclusive across the age groups.

Chat with EAA Official over TEA

Zena Kamash

Institution: Royal Holloway, University of London

Position in the EAA: Deputy-Editor-in-Chief, *European Journal of Archaeology*

EAA Member since: 2019

Image courtesy of Z. Kamash

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

Z. Kamash: As editors of *EJA*, Cate (Frieman; Editor-in-Chief) and I read every submission to the journal. This not only gives us a great overview of the current state of European archaeology, but also allows us to shape major current narratives. One of my proudest moments was publishing the manifesto from the European Society of Black and Allied Archaeologists in 2021. Working with up-and-coming scholars submitting to *EJA* is particularly satisfying as this is often their first foray into academic publishing; we hope we make it an enjoyable experience for them.

TEA: What/How does archaeology contribute to society at large?

Z. Kamash: I'm a strong believer that the archaeological sector can help communities negotiate change, develop a renewed sense of place and understand more deeply the diverse and important heritage that surrounds us. I've recently completed a British Academy-funded project (the [ChEWI Project](#)) that explores how crafting, heritage and wellbeing can be brought together to support communities who have experienced conflict. Watching tiny threads of social bonds repairing in our workshops has been the most rewarding part of my career to date.

At right: Kamash at Avebury. Image courtesy of Z. Kamash

TEA: Describe your workspace in five words or less.

Z. Kamash: Teetering book piles, plus cat.

TEA: What is your best/worst/funniest/oddest archaeology/work story?

Z. Kamash: I used to attend a Materiality Discussion Group and spent an embarrassingly long amount of time thinking that people were discussing ‘Kittens’, rather than ‘Giddens’.

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out/joining the EAA?

Z. Kamash: Find your people at EAA and have fun exploring new ideas and friendships. If you think something needs to change, be bold and speak out. Know your own worth. You are the future of archaeology and your voice matters.

At left: Kamash at Bamburgh Castle, Northumberland UK.

TEA: Do you go to archaeological sites on vacation, or do you do other things?

Z. Kamash: I can never resist visiting an archaeological site or several on holiday. My husband, Peter Banks, is also an archaeologist (a pottery specialist at Cotswold Archaeology), so we both love finding a site or little museum we’ve not been to before. This included snacking on wedding cake at Belas Knap Long Barrow on our honeymoon!

Above: Wedding cake at the barrow. Image courtesy of Z. Kamash

Meet a Member over TEA

Robert Staniuk

Nationality: Polish

Institution: University College London

Position: Research Fellow

EAA Member since: 2014

Photo by Sarah Martini, courtesy of R. Staniuk

TEA: Why do you do archaeology/How did you decide to do it?

R. Staniuk: I was born in Pomerania, a region of Central Europe frequently exchanged between Germany, Poland and (occasionally) Sweden. My grandparents—as did many from their generation—moved there after World War II, which meant that questions about belonging, origins or history would often yield only short-term answers. Fascination with history would eventually lead me towards archaeology, especially prehistoric archaeology, as it seemed to me to be more linked to long-term histories of people rather than states or conquests.

In time, I discovered that while the bread and butter of archaeology is solving the puzzles left to us by people in the past, it is as frequently a puzzle left to us by other scholars, with their own partial answers, suggestions and the best solutions with which they could come up given the tools at hand. I think around that time I also started my course on the Bronze Age, which to me, remains one of the most interesting moments in European prehistory. At that point, all the pieces fell into the right place, and while I often question whether it is a sane career choice, I find it difficult to picture myself doing anything else!

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

R. Staniuk: The project I am currently part of "[COREX. From CORrelations to EXplanations: towards a new European prehistory](#)" investigates the relationship between patterns of genetic and cultural changes between 6000-500 BC. My role in COREX is to build a bridge between genetic and cultural data in archaeology, so we can start tracing when and where the two threads come close together and when and where they come apart. That bridge is a direct association of aDNA and archaeological cultural data, so that we can actually investigate the relevance of cultural associations for explaining genetic groups. I believe that this approach will give us a better grasp of the human past, and as aDNA from around the world becomes increasingly available, we'll be able to update our understanding of global prehistory more efficiently and—more importantly—more scientifically.

TEA: In your opinion, what is the biggest issue facing archaeology today?

R. Staniuk: Firstly, the main challenge to all academia is the insufficiently challenged rise of wealth inequality affecting research budgets and researcher salaries, discouraging people with excellent ideas or skills to pursue academic careers. Secondly, though climate change will impact every aspect of our lives, specifically for archaeology, I believe it will require a complete reconsideration of heritage management protocols as sites which one would consider ‘protected’ will be at risk of destruction as our living conditions change.

When it comes to regional challenges, the on-going Russian invasion of Ukraine is a major concern for European archaeology, as it directly affects the lives of our colleagues and their loved ones, brings destruction to key sites of Eurasian (pre)history, hinders safe research (or renders it completely impossible) and, finally, brings great uncertainty about our future.

TEA: How do you see archaeology changing in the future?

R. Staniuk: I believe that the methods we are concerned about right now (AI, problems with integrating genetic data from individuals, objects, or sediments with cultural information) will be quickly embraced by archaeology, leading to more formalized research on general social questions. This process might discourage some scholars with a more regional or aspect-based approach but eventually, the availability of scientific models and data will be integrated for better narratives about the human past. During this time, we will likely discover new questions of truly global scale and significance, which will likely transform the discipline immensely. That is of course, if funding for archaeology remains in place and the overall employment conditions improve! Last but absolutely not least, this process cannot happen without the constant work of local archaeologists, making the discoveries and publishing them, so we all can benefit from their findings.

At right: Staniuk giving a talk at the 2023 AM on the opportunities and challenges of integrating genetic and cultural data in archaeological research. Photo by S. Reiter.

TEA: If you could have a conversation with any archaeologist living or dead, who would it be, and what would you choose as the topic?

R. Staniuk: Not one but two, if possible. I’d like to ask Gustaf Kossinna and Józef Kostrzewski—a master and his student—how it could be that they both used the same method and came up with completely different and opposing results and yet nevertheless did not simply reject the method as unscientific. I like to think that this simple conclusion would have immensely affected where we are right now in terms of history as well as a discipline.

TEA: What archaeology literature are you reading right now?

R. Staniuk: I was fascinated by P. Turchin’s “End Times: Elites, Counter-Elites, and the Path of Political Disintegration”, so I am right now going through his “Ultrasociety: How 10,000 Years of War Made Humans the Greatest Cooperators on Earth”. It’s a very exciting read, especially in the context of the often-polarized discussion about the importance of cooperation over competition. I think he demonstrates really well that one cannot exist without the other.

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

R. Staniuk: Don’t be afraid to make mistakes! (You’ll learn from them, and you’ll learn faster!) Always appreciate criticism of your work. (It means that someone cares enough to get into details and can help you find better solutions). Finally, be kind. (It never hurts.) The rest, I think is, hard work and luck.

Above: Staniuk collecting data at the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in Budapest. The ceramic materials were from Kakucs-Turján, an Early-Middle Bronze Age multi-layered, fortified settlement in Central Hungary. Photo by Sarah Martini.

Report

Conserving and investigating the Uffington White Horse

Adrian Cox

The National Trust

Etched across the edge of the Berkshire Downs and near to their highest point, the Uffington White Horse is an iconic image, and is amongst the best-known of Britain's chalk hill figures. See Figure 1. Thanks to archaeological science, we also know that it is the oldest of them, dating from the late Bronze Age. The intentions of its creators have been the subject of much debate and may always prove somewhat elusive, but there is no doubt that the significance of the 120 m long carving is enhanced by the way it has been cared for by local people through the centuries. This important work continues right up to the present day.

Figure 1. An aerial view of White Horse Hill, with scouring underway. Image © National Trust Images/Mike Calnan/James Dobson).

The significance of White Horse Hill

White Horse Hill is part of a wider prehistoric landscape, which includes Uffington Castle, an Iron-Age hill fort, a flat-topped hill called Dragon Hill (in folklore, the site where Saint George slayed the dragon, e.g. Rev. Francis Wise, 1738), barrows representing the sites of prehistoric and later burials, and a fascinating geological feature known as The Manger, created by glacial meltwaters towards the end

of the last Ice Age. The combined aspects of the wider geological, historical and ecological setting contribute to the significance of this dramatic landscape.

A short distance further to the southwest lies Wayland's Smithy, an Early Neolithic chambered long barrow, among the indications that this area was already an important place before the White Horse was created around 3000 years ago. Linking these and many other archaeological features is an ancient route; the Ridgeway is regarded as one of the oldest known routes in Britain used for migration and trade.

As well as including a number of scheduled ancient monuments, much of the White Horse Hill landscape also has a Site of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI) designation as the unimproved chalk grassland which once covered much of the Downs survives here with its rich flora and fauna. The rare glacial sediments that form part of the Manger also contribute to the SSSI designation.

The continued use of the White Horse Hill landscape over thousands of years is exemplified by the re-use of prehistoric burial sites in the Romano-British period, a time during which Uffington Castle was also re-used. This highlights the importance of the landscape to successive peoples over a very long time span. The re-use of burial sites indicates ongoing religious and ritual importance, and it appears that the White Horse itself has been held in high regard throughout this long period right into the present day. Whilst it appears that the form and character of the Horse has remained largely constant, its meaning to local people may have changed to suit different cultures and beliefs.

The meaning of the Horse has long been the subject of debate and new theories continue to emerge. For centuries, people speculated about the age of the Horse and, thus, its meaning. For example, was it a marker to celebrate Alfred the Great's victory over the Danes, or was it instead something created to mark the arrival of the first Anglo-Saxon settlers? Schwyzer (1999) covers the history of antiquarian discussions over the dating of figure in some detail. Thanks to archaeological science (see below), most of these theories can be discounted.

The Uffington Horse is markedly different from the other horse images appearing on Britain's hills, and it was arguably the inspiration for some of those others. It is a dynamic and sleek figure in contrast to the others, with a form that suggests galloping across the hillside. Perhaps with this fluidity of movement comes a fluidity of meaning. It is clear, though, that the galloping White Horse and its landscape, through such a long period of cultural use, represent not only exceptionally high prehistoric cultural and social significance, but a continued cultural and social significance right up to the present day.

The scouring and chalking of the Horse

The survival of this iconic figure relies upon regular maintenance—the control of encroaching vegetation and the cleaning of the uppermost layer of chalk, known as 'scouring' and 'chalking'. Historical records of the scouring begin to appear in the 18th century, but this regular activity by the local community must stretch much further into the past and reveals the very real and enduring significance of this monument to the population of the vicinity. Without regular maintenance, the White Horse would disappear under a layer of soil and vegetation. It is a huge testament to the determination and care of local people that the Horse has survived for thousands of years during the period of occupation of Uffington Castle, through the Romano-British period and even through Saxon

and medieval times. This careful work has resulted in the constant renewal and refreshment of the image.

The scouring and chalking process involves clearing any grass and other vegetation from the surface of the chalk, working towards the edges of the outline, and then adding more locally quarried chalk to the surface to replace that lost through erosion. This is then beaten into the surface. The process has possibly resulted in minor changes to, or fluctuations in, the outline of the figure. However, recent research has shown that the outline has remained remarkably constant since accurate records began.

The earliest mention of periodic scourings was by Thomas Baskerville (1681); such work also featured in an epic poem, 'The Ballad of the White Horse' by G. K. Chesterton in 1911. More detail surrounding the activities was offered by Thomas Hughes (1859). Hughes' is a semi-fictional account of the last great festival associated with the scouring, held in 1857. Hughes himself was born in Uffington, in the vale below the White Horse and was also the author of 'Tom Brown's Schooldays' (Hughes 1857). He notes that scourings took place every few years, and describes the festivities, known as the 'pastime' in some depth. He also referred to an earlier event (held in 1776) which included horse races, donkey races, foot and sack races and the prizes allocated to the winners of the competitions. There were also customs like climbing of a greasy pole and racing down the steep slope of the Manger in pursuit of a runaway cheese! This social gathering and its associated rituals may have been quite deeply rooted in the past. No doubt it gave an opportunity for people to meet, trade and perhaps form relationships, although it sounds like there would have also been a few bumps and bruises involved!

Moving forward to modern times, the National Trust has organised annual scouring and chalking of the White Horse in recent decades, involving numerous volunteers from the local community, including its own staff and those of English Heritage (the land is in National Trust ownership and English Heritage guardianship). Volunteers involved in this regular conservation activity appear to enjoy taking part in an activity with such strong and meaningful links to the past. This is generally organised over school holidays, and volunteers are still accepted. Though the 2024 dates have yet to be released, you can check the [National Trust's webpage](#) for details. The process of regularly scouring the chalk figure represents a longstanding and important community activity and illustrates the social value placed on this landscape by local people over a very long period. The community's longstanding care both enhances the cultural significance of the White Horse while also ensuring its survival.

Archaeological investigations

The distinctive profile of the White Horse has altered only slightly over the millennia, while its position and overall character appear to be essentially as intended. Having been covered over with turf during the Second World War to prevent *Luftwaffe* bomber pilots using it as a navigational aid, 20th-century archaeological investigations began during the restoration of the figure by W. F. Grimes in 1950. A trench across the 'beak' protruding from the Horse's head revealed two phases of construction and helped determine that the figure was formed by cutting a trench into the hillside and filling it in with chalk blocks. The natural chalk lay over 1m below the current ground surface.

Surveys of the site were undertaken by the Oxford Archaeology Unit (later Oxford Archaeology) during the 1980s, and Grimes' 1950 trench was re-opened in 1990-91 to re-examine the stratigraphy. This research made the application of the OSL (optically stimulated luminescence) dating technique possible, and from this the figure was dated to the late Bronze Age. This was a time when horses were

a relatively recent introduction to the British Isles and were associated with power and prestige. Oxford Archaeology's investigations from 1989-1995 are reported by David Miles *et al* (2003) and David Miles has since published an excellent book seeking to analyse many aspects of the White Horse (Miles 2019).

Recent archaeological research

Following a drone survey of the Horse and the use of digital overlays to identify minor changes in the figure's outline in 2023, small archaeological trenches were excavated at the head and the neck. These removed only the turf in order to determine the extent of the shrinkage in width. See Figure 2. The results of this partnership project involving David Miles, Simon Palmer, the National Trust and English Heritage, will inform work to return the profile to its traditional form under archaeological supervision, thus aiding the future conservation and management of the figure.

Figure 2. The author during the 2023 archaeological research at the head and neck of the White Horse. Image courtesy of A. Cox.

Personal reflections and conclusions

As The National Trust's archaeologist, I have been involved in the study and care of the White Horse for a relatively short time. However, watching and working alongside a large gathering of enthusiastic volunteers scouring and re-chalking the figure gives one the feeling of a satisfying community endeavour. All those involved are genuinely enjoying being part of history and part of an impressive team effort to look after something important and iconic.

The landscape here is breathtakingly beautiful, with a big, ever-changing sky dotted with skylarks and soared over by majestic red kites. There can be a real sense of joy about the whole process. People

have been drawn to the landscape over thousands of years, to live and work in it, to celebrate and to bury their dead. Today's visitors come with a sense of fascination and wonder. The annual scouring is a labour of love; a work of care and of renewal. The White Horse is not only hugely significant; it is also a symbol of continuity and a remarkable survival.

Acknowledgments

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Project Overview

Preserving Ukrainian Legacy: Midway Reflections and Lessons Learnt

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As the Russian-Ukrainian war continues, the prospect of a swift resolution grows increasingly distant. This ongoing situation poses escalating challenges for Ukrainian archaeologists and cultural heritage experts. Historic sites and collections are increasingly threatened, while the number of professionals able to address these challenges is growing smaller. Amidst these difficulties, the urgency of preserving Ukraine's cultural heritage only intensifies.

The war has clearly shown the numerous risks and challenges facing Ukrainian cultural heritage, including the critical task of preserving archaeological landscapes that now find themselves on the front lines. The group most involved in this effort has been the Archaeological Landscapes Monitoring Group, whose ongoing work is outlined in *TEA 74* ([Shydlovskyy, Telizhenko & Ivakin 2022](#)). However, as European cultural heritage in Ukraine faces daily threats of damage and destruction, numerous organizations have come together to respond, embracing various practices and projects to support preservation. Reflecting the trends of the last few decades, one of the most dynamic responses has been through the digitization of Ukrainian cultural heritage. Here, we will share our personal experiences with one such an initiative and briefly account for lessons we have learned from it.

To begin with, most Ukrainian cultural heritage experts agree that the war has served not as a creator but rather as an aggrandizer of pre-existing challenges within the realm of cultural heritage research, curation and preservation in the country. Among the critical issues now magnified by the conflict is the inherent difficulty of preserving and monitoring archaeological sites on the front lines, exacerbated by the lack of comprehensive records of these places. Additionally, a lack of international awareness of Ukrainian history and archaeology often results in European academics unwittingly engaging with Russian scholars despite ethical guidelines by the EAA which advise against such interactions. Finally, Ukrainian heritage experts have limited capacities for the digitization of archaeological heritage (especially movable objects) due to limited resources.

Digitizing Ukraine's cultural heritage is a complex interdisciplinary task that is simultaneously confronted by shortages in resources, expertise and technology. These shortages are deeply interlinked; addressing one in isolation is ineffective. Merely equipping Ukrainian cultural heritage professionals without imparting the necessary skills or resources will not lead to productive use of the equipment. Similarly, offering advanced digitization training courses is futile without access to the necessary technology. Moreover, even well-trained and -equipped experts need adequate time and financial support to travel, collect, process, store and present the data. These are not challenges that can be solved by Ukrainians in isolation, particularly as the country grapples with pressing survival

challenges on a daily basis. Thus, our approach to designing digitization projects has been holistic, striving to simultaneously equip Ukrainian cultural heritage professionals with the necessary resources, skills and technologies to foster meaningful progress.

The first project, arranged by the NGO “Archaic” team from autumn 2022 to spring 2023, was called “[3D History for Ukraine](#)” and immediately revealed the multifaceted challenges inherent in digitization projects in Ukraine. Initiated as a fully crowd-funded, volunteer-led project, it aimed to catalyse digitization efforts with limited resources. Leveraging support from the World Archaeological Congress and Heritage Media Group, the Archaic team arranged a two-day online conference to raise donations for digitization equipment. The plan was for a specially trained team to commence the digitization effort with hopes of scaling up as soon as tangible outcomes were achieved.

While solid in theory, the strategy quickly ran into practical challenges. Despite our fundraising efforts, we fell short of the amount needed to purchase high-quality laser scanning equipment, partly because distributors did not offer discounts. As a result, the team had to use a more labour-intensive approach that combined less-than-ideal laser scans with photogrammetry, requiring the use of four to five different software solutions for each model.

Aligning this complex process with the expertise of our volunteer team in Ukraine was challenging. It took nearly two months to train volunteers in this workflow, and these efforts were delayed by a further three months due to equipment delivery times. During our attempted roll out of this methodology, half of the volunteers were conscripted into the military, forcing them to leave the project. Despite these setbacks, we succeeded in producing a dozen 3D models of artefacts. See Figure 3. These datasets mark the beginning of our digitization efforts, but they did not meet our initial expectations and fell short in terms of quality. However, the project was not without its successes. We improved our data management practices with advice from colleagues at the Open Context Lab and demonstrated our ability to develop technological solutions in difficult conditions. This project ultimately served as a valuable learning experience and a solid foundation for our future work.

Leveraging the lessons learned from the pilot project, we started collaborating with CyArk, a non-profit organization based in California, USA. CyArk’s mission is to “unlock the power of 3D technology to make the world’s cultural heritage accessible to new audiences and future generations.” Together, we analyzed the outcomes of the “3D History for Ukraine” project to enhance the efficacy of our next foray into digitization in the challenging environment of wartime Ukraine. The new initiative, “Preserving Ukrainian Legacy: Enhancing Cultural Heritage Protection through 3D Digitization Training and Collaboration” was supported by the US State Department through the Ambassador’s Fund for Cultural Preservation program and was designed to address the three main digitization issues described above with a complex integrated solution. It aimed, thus, to provide comprehensive training, equipment and additional resources to three selected museum institutions: the “Khortytsia” National Reserve, the Dmytro Yavornitskiy Dnipro National Historical Museum and the National Museum of the History of Ukraine.

CyArk’s training expertise was integral to the success of the training activities. CyArk provided both online instruction and a week of hands-on in-person training at Jagiellonian University in Krakow. See Figure 4.

Figure 3. Laser scanning at the Kyiv National University within the “3D History for Ukraine” project.

Figure 4. Training activities at Jagiellonian University. Image by Kacey Hadick.

Twelve representatives from the three participating museums as well as the “Archaic” group traveled to Krakow to gain important hands-on training with the equipment and review 3D documentation methods. Crucially, the training fostered a supportive network, which continues today. This allows participants to seek assistance and share insights on challenges encountered both during and after the project's completion.

During the training, participating institutions received computers and photogrammetric equipment, enabling hands-on practice with equipment that became the property of each participating institution. See Figure 5. This approach allowed them to familiarize themselves with the technology, conduct practical tests, complete assignments and address any immediate queries. Each kit was a bit unique, adjusted to the needs of the particular museum partner.

Figure 5. An overview of the photogrammetric kit. A — Camera (Sony A7R III); B — Camera lenses (Tamron 24mm/ Sigma 105mm Lens); C — Lens polarizers/filters; D — Camera tripod; E — Laptop (Lenovo IdeaPad Pro); F — Hard Drive and storage cards; G — Backpack; H — Lights and stands for artefact lighting; I — Scale bars; J — Shutter release; K — Color card; L — Macro rail; M — Artefact turntable; N — Software (RealityCapture, Autodesk ReCap Pro, Capture One).

Following the training, all participants returned to Ukraine and their respective institutions to begin the digitization and data processing efforts. Our goal was for each institution to digitize 50 to 60 priority artefacts deemed most urgent for various reasons. See Figure 6. In total, 180 models were created during this initial phase. Throughout this phase, “Archaic” played a supportive role, aiding in the production of 3D models, data monitoring, workflow management etc., ensuring each team had the necessary resources and support.

Figure 6. Practical part of “Preserving Ukrainian Legacy” in the National Museum of the History of Ukraine. Oleksandra Ivanova is meeting the Trypillian figurine. Image by Tim Hordiienko.

By simultaneously providing museum partners with training, equipment, and additional resources, a structured framework was established that effectively launched the digitization process. This achievement was made possible through several strategic design elements:

1. The project team was multidisciplinary, encompassing archaeologists, museum professionals, and digitization specialists from both Ukraine and the USA. This diversity enabled each team to make informed tactical decisions throughout the process.;
2. CyArk and Archaic demonstrated a deep understanding of the unique needs of Ukrainian stakeholders, committing significant effort to ensure the sustainability of digitization efforts well beyond the lifespan of this particular project;
3. Museum participants played an active role in the decision-making process, ensuring their voices were heard and allowing for real-time adjustments to the project's direction as needed;
4. Flexibility was built into the entire workflow, allowing it to adapt to the ever-changing circumstances of a country affected by conflict.

Although, to date, the project has only applied to a small sample of the collections of three museums, it highlighted the rich diversity and scope of Ukrainian cultural heritage. See Figures 7-8. We explored a wide range of artefacts, from Upper Paleolithic art to 19th-century shipwrecks, employing various methods to examine objects that, in some cases, had been concealed for nearly a century. While the Eneolithic Trypillian culture's painted vessels and female figurines have gained recognition within the global academic community, many unique artefacts have yet to be fully discovered and appreciated. Noteworthy among these are the exquisite Upper Paleolithic ivory figurines from Mizyn, excavated in the early 20th century, and the decorated anthropomorphic stelae from the Eneolithic and Bronze Age. Despite their significance and previous scholarly attention, these artefacts have seldom been represented in 3D or examined from a digital perspective. Reflecting on the project's conclusion, it is time for some introspection regarding the work undertaken and the curiosities encountered. While our observations are drawn from Ukraine, the insights garnered are broadly applicable.

Figure 7. QR-code for Archaic Sketchfab, where the models are uploaded.

Figure 8. The variety of artefacts digitized during the “Preserving Ukrainian Legacy” project.

Numerous digitization efforts have emerged in Ukraine since the onset of the war, yet most have concentrated on large-scale items like monuments and architectural sites, leaving portable artefacts relatively unaddressed. This oversight is particularly glaring given the vast quantity of portable cultural heritage items compared to larger objects, many of which were not evacuated or remained on display due to logistical constraints. These smaller artefacts—often crucial for archaeological research—merit as much attention as does more visible architectural heritage.

Our preliminary research in advance of the project revealed a stark absence of initiatives aimed at educating cultural heritage professionals on digitization techniques such as photogrammetry or laser scanning. Instead, the focus has been on digitizing specific objects or categories of objects, a practice we view as a significant oversight and a disservice to the potential development of Ukrainian cultural heritage institutions. To effectively safeguard against targeted cultural heritage destruction, these institutions must be equipped with the necessary methods and tools.

Moreover, we encountered museums that, despite having received digitization equipment or training, were unable to utilize these resources effectively due to other constraints, highlighting a disconnect between museums and supporting organizations. We firmly hold that the success of digitization initiatives in Ukraine hinges on the active involvement of Ukrainian cultural heritage professionals, rather than relegation to foreign entities or private companies with technological prowess.

Constraining the contribution of local experts not only reflects a colonialist mindset but also undermines their capacity for autonomous growth, essential for the digitization and preservation of Ukraine's cultural legacy.

Our collaboration with Ukrainian museums revealed the unique administrative structures, curation practices and data policies within each institution, emphasizing the importance of personalized approaches in these partnerships. The project underscored a common gap in expertise: cultural heritage professionals often lack knowledge of digitization techniques, and digitization experts may not be familiar with the policies and practices cultural institutions follow when sharing cultural resources with the public and/or academic audiences. This disconnect can lead to projects failing to achieve their intended outcomes, leading institutions to be hesitant about embarking on similar initiatives in the future due to a fear of repeating past mistakes.

An additional challenge identified was the widespread lack of familiarity with 3D modelling techniques in the digitization of cultural heritage. The legal framework in Ukraine is still evolving to adequately address the nuances of digital cultural heritage data and its protections. It is essential to prioritize the clear articulation of rights related to digital heritage data throughout the lifespan of the project. Moreover, the importance of the accuracy of 3D models is often overlooked by documentation specialists and cultural institutions, despite its critical role in research and the integrity of digitization projects. We argue that a comprehensive understanding of 3D modelling accuracy must be developed and integrated as a fundamental component of any digital heritage documentation. Without this focus, there is a risk of losing vital data. Furthermore, accuracy serves as an indispensable tool for quality control, particularly crucial for the successful coordination of projects across remote teams.

A key insight from “Preserving Ukrainian Legacy” that we will carry forward is the instructional importance of paradata. In contrast to metadata (which describes the data collected), paradata provides insights into the data acquisition process and its variation across different artefacts. This information proved crucial for our team in Ukraine, particularly in selecting data acquisition parameters and comparing digitization practices across various objects.

The project's flexibility proved vital, allowing adjustments in response to wartime challenges. This adaptability, coupled with a minimized reliance on external entities, was crucial for navigating the uncertainties of war. Many objects that museums set as their initial priorities were inaccessible during the project, so we were forced to find substitutions. Due to shelling and the complicated working schedules at the museums, the digitization process went longer than anticipated and was additionally complicated by safety regulations.

The war transformed even minor initiatives into high-risk ventures with numerous potential pitfalls. Thus, reducing dependency on external parties—such as government bodies, transport services, and cultural heritage experts not part of the project team—proved to be the most effective strategy for project implementation. The greater our direct control over the project's processes, the more secure and successful they became.

In conclusion, our reflections distil into several guiding principles for digitization projects globally: avoiding colonialist attitudes, embracing transdisciplinarity, maintaining flexibility and ensuring

constant communication with all participants. The last point is perhaps the most crucial, underscoring the importance of support and validation in times of need.

Insight

What is E-RIHS, what is it for and why it is so crucial for European cultural heritage

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Who we are

The [European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science \(E-RIHS\)](#) comprises an array of formally-organized research organizations, universities, restoration centers and cultural institutions which are distributed across fourteen countries both within and outside of the European Union (Belgium, Cyprus, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and the United Kingdom). This setup ensures a wide geographic distribution and facilitates a cohesive approach to fostering advancements in heritage science. The inclusion of the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM) as a permanent observer further solidifies this integrated framework, reinforcing its contribution to the global heritage science community.

E-RIHS' vision and mission

E-RIHS' vision is to ensure that heritage remains meaningful, relevant and accessible for the benefit of present and future citizens. In pursuit of this, E-RIHS addresses its services to tangible heritage materials with the aim of uncovering the complex cultural and historical layers embedded within them. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these materials is pivotal to better interpreting the past and preserving it. E-RIHS aims to safeguard not only the physical condition of cultural heritage, but also its intangible meaning. Achieving a deep understanding of these materials is crucial for a more detailed interpretation of the past and its preservation. Thus, we aim to protect both the physical state and the intrinsic value of cultural heritage. The mission of E-RIHS is to serve the heritage science community by providing scholars and practitioners with centralized access to expertise, know-how, research capabilities and resources. This is facilitated through a combination of physical and virtual platforms which are designed to support a diverse array of research, from object-focused case studies

to large-scale longer-term research projects. Additionally, E-RIHS champions the adoption of best practices and offers advanced training through the Heritage Science Academy.

A New Paradigm in Heritage Science

The uniqueness of E-RIHS lies in overcoming traditional approaches. For an example, one need look no further than ‘science for art’, which kicks off the new, widely interdisciplinary domain of heritage science in which hard sciences and humanities join forces with equal importance and roles. Since the inception of its first European project in 1999, E-RIHS has been striving to open the road to modern heritage science and be the global reference research infrastructure for improving understanding and the sustainable preservation of heritage objects and sites. Over the years, E-RIHS has expanded through the support of various EU projects (such as [IPERION HS](#)) and has attracted prestigious institutions from across Europe to its community. The aim is to phase out the isolation and/or duplication of efforts and to develop a paradigm founded on excellence, joint research, and networking.

A shared roadmap for boosting European research

In 2016, E-RIHS entered the ESFRI Roadmap: the European Strategy to encourage Member States and Associated Countries to develop national *roadmaps* for research infrastructures. We are on track to become an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) in 2024. From this time, E-RIHS will be a Consortium with full legal capacity and a formal structure. The E-RIHS Central Hub is in Florence, Italy. From that location, it coordinates the [National Nodes](#) which correspond to the countries participating in the ERIC.

What we do

E-RIHS supports researchers by providing access to its laboratories, cutting-edge instruments and staff expertise through research projects of scientific excellence. Researchers can submit their proposals and—after a strict selection process—winners have access to the laboratories and instruments selected in their proposals. With some exceptions, access is free of charge.

What we secure

E-RIHS facilitates cutting-edge research and innovation for scholars and practitioners through four integrated platforms: ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB. ARCHLAB offers access to organized scientific information contained in mostly unpublished datasets from the archives and libraries of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions. DIGILAB helps researchers to make use of databases for their research and the handling of their data. FIXLAB provides access to fixed laboratories with sophisticated instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry. Finally, MOLAB provides access to a set of mobile equipment (it moves across the EU) for *in-situ* non-invasive measurement of artworks, collections, monuments and sites. See Figures 9-11.

Figure 9. ARCLAB. Samples at the Opificio delle Pietre dure’s archive in Florence, Italy.

Figure 10. FIXLAB. PIXE (Particle-induced X-ray emission) and RBS (Rutherford backscattering spectrometry) at AGLAE (Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées, Paris, France) on Iranian lustre tiles to investigate the elemental composition.

Figure 11. MOLAB. Diagnostic investigation on Van Gogh's "Sunflowers". The technique used is hyperspectral imaging in the visible range. This allows the analysis and non-invasive documentation of various types of polychrome artefacts (e.g., paintings on canvas and wooden panels, illuminated manuscripts, frescoes and wall paintings) to investigate of the nature of the colors and their state of preservation for conservation and restoration purposes. Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam, the Netherlands.

What we develop

E-RIHS aims to develop standard practices, protocols and an interoperable ecosystem of data, tools and services for heritage science research. The goal is to guarantee a joint scientific approach which is uniform at both the European and international level.

What we foster

E-RIHS' main effort focus is to guarantee an interdisciplinary approach to research for all users' communities: science, art, engineering, archaeology, chemistry and physics as applied to cultural heritage, anthropology, and digital humanities. It is for this reason that, under the umbrella of the Heritage Science Academy, specialist webinars on various scientific topics are regularly organized, along with Doctoral Summer Schools and Training Camps across Europe which are aimed at training the next generations of heritage scientists. See Figure 12.

What we can offer the archaeological community

By participating in the yearly calls for access, archaeologists can present projects ranging from the analysis of an object to that of a site. We can offer access to laboratories, instruments and techniques

Figure 12. Training Camp on Innovative Techniques for Cultural Heritage: Knowledge and characterization of archaeological sites and finds. The aim was to offer participants a broad overview of issues in the field of conservation and analysis of archaeological sites and finds and to gain experience in finding solutions to the scenarios with which they were confronted. Photo from Alghero (Porto Conte), Sardinia, Italy.

Figure 13. FIXLAB. Investigation of an ancient gold artefact with *PIXE* (Particle-induced X-ray emission), a technique used for determining the elemental composition of a material or a sample which allows for the detection of original parts from forgeries, subsequent additions and restorations.

for diverse needs. With the large-scale laboratories of FIXLAB, it is possible to conduct new analyses on ceramics, bones (for a DNA analysis) metals (for the analysis of alloys and manufacturing processes) and/or glass, etc. With the mobile MOLAB laboratories, hidden sites, submerged structures and complex architectures can be unveiled and digitized. See Figure 13.

Figure 14. MOLAB. Diagnostic investigation on an Egyptian coffin by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy to study the polichromy of the artefact. Museo Arqueológico Nacional in Madrid). MOLAB access from the IPERION CH project, one of the heritage science community's first successfully managed projects.

MOLAB can also offer LiDAR (Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging) and multispectral drone imaging. LiDAR's ability to penetrate vegetation allows it to bring to light archaeological structures and topographic variations of cultural interest that may be unknown (or partially known) due to difficulties in detecting them from the ground. This technology on an aerial platform opens new research perspectives in studies of the human past. Multi-sensor platforms on drone allows for the identification, georeferencing and insertion of proxy indicators into the map, such as changes in humidity (damp-marks), changes in vegetation growth (cropmarks) and the presence of organic materials on the surface attributable to the presence of underground structures. Importantly, our researchers can also offer scientific support in the use of all those instruments, such as the Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), which allows investigation of buried structures in a sort of virtual excavation preparatory to the archaeological one. Investigations of this type have been carried out e.g., at the Roman Forum in Rome, Italy and the Church of the Holy Sepulcher in Jerusalem, Israel. Shallow marine geophysical investigations to detect buried archaeological features in a coastal area have been carried out to investigate the Roman site of Baiae in Naples, Italy. Speaking of archaeological objects, they can

be investigated in their elemental and chromatic composition, by using for instance X-ray fluorescence (XRF) for the study of the elemental composition of the surface, Raman for the molecular characterization of the constituent materials, or the digital/optical microscope for the collection of micrographs of the areas investigated. See Figure 14. In the case of objects of historical-archaeological importance, 3D reconstructions can also be assembled, e.g., for use in museums. A catalogue of all available instruments and techniques will be shortly available on the E-RIHS website.

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International heritage alert

Threat of damage to the Vingen rock art area and its pristine surrounding landscape

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The Vingen rock art area in the municipality of Bremanger, western Norway is one of the largest and best-preserved rock art concentrations in Northern Europe. Set in a dramatic landscape, the area is surrounded by steep mountains to the south, east and north and exposed to harsh western sea, wind and weather conditions. Thousands of petroglyphs from the Stone Age have been documented on large rock panels, big boulders and smaller stones surrounding the minor Vingen fjord. The images display interactions between red deer, human skeletons, animal-headed staffs, sea mammals and geometric images, and may be understood as a pictorial language providing unique insight into past narratives. Numerous archaeological traces and settlement sites associated with the producers of the rock art have also been found in the area. Much remains to be further investigated, but research has so far revealed a rich archaeological source for the future dating and decoding of the rock art. See Figures 15-16.

To the shock of the international heritage community, the Norwegian government recently approved the establishment of a stone quarry for the extraction of Devonian sandstone in the proximity of the Vingen rock art area. The quarry (and associated shipping port) will have a devastating impact on both the rock art and the larger surrounding area, disrupting the historic landscape, as well as native, Red-Listed species.

Figure 15. One of several hundred panels with rock art in the Vingen area, with red deer displayed in motion. In the background the peak Hornelen, Northern Europe's tallest sea cliff. The vegetated promontory Vingeneset on the other side of the fjord is the location of 18 panels with rock art and approximately one hundred petroglyphs. Photo by T. Løddøen.

Figure 16. Panoramic view of the Vingen protected landscape area. Vingeneset to the left, with approximately 100 petroglyphs and the Vingen terrace, with the densest concentration of rock art to the right; over 300 panels and more than 2000 individual figures. Photo by T. Løddøen.

More than a century of documentation and research

The rock art first became publicly known in 1912 when the first paper on Vingen was published by the lawyer, amateur archaeologist and mountain explorer Kristian Bing. He was introduced to the site by local inhabitants. See Figure 17. Bing's paper is saturated with his overwhelming enthusiasm. For example, he refers to Vingen as "Nature's own colossal museum of rock art" (Bing 1912: 36). Since then, numerous papers and books have been published, covering a wide variety of research aims and approaches to the rock art area (e.g. Bøe 1932; Hallström 1938; Bakka 1973, 1979, Løddøen and Mandt 2010, 2012, Walderhaug 2010). See Figures 18a, 18b and 19. With its unique rock art and contemporary archaeological remains, the area has huge unexploited future research potential. The site has been central to many research and management projects and programmes aimed at the protection of rock art (Løddøen 2010). Since the beginning of the 1990s more than 100 million NOK of public funding has been invested by the Directorate for Cultural Heritage, The Norwegian Environment Agency, Vestland County Council, the County Governor of Vestland, the University of Bergen and the University Museum of Bergen.

Figure 17. Documentation procedures in 1913, a year after the site was first documented. Photo Gustaf Hallström.

Figure 18a. The Hardbakken panel with more than 130 images of red deer and human skeletons. In the background the island of Hennøya and the partly hidden Aksla mountain to the left. Photo by T. Lødøen.

Figure 18b. Tracing of the Hardbakken rock art. Image produced by Arkikon AS.

Figure 19. One of the many red deer images from the Hardbakken panel. Photo by T. Lødøen.

The Vingen rock art was produced at the end of the Late Mesolithic (Lødøen 2013). See Figure 20. In addition to the rock art, Vingen also has extensive archaeological remains still preserved *in situ*. Several small-scale archaeological excavations have provided valuable information from these sources; independent investigations date the rock art production to 6900-6200 Cal BP (Hjelle and Lødøen 2017). Amongst the remains retrieved are tools for the production of rock art and smaller rocks and slabs with petroglyphs. The latter can be understood as portable rock art. In addition, several dwelling depressions have been found, most likely constructed and occupied by the producers of the rock art. These sources are far from fully prospected or documented.

Figure 20. Depictions of red deer and animal headed staffs. Photo by T. Lødøen.

Today, the Vingen area can only be reached by boat. The surrounding area remains one of the largest on the outer coast of western Norway that still maintains a road-free gradient from fjord to mountains. Cascading waterfalls, circular winds, sea currents and tidal conditions place the rock art within a dramatic landscape context. See Figure 21. The enclosed rock art area with its surrounding steep mountains creates a natural cathedral, enhanced during winter and late autumn when the surrounding peaks prevent sunlight from reaching the area.

Figure 21. Reoccurring wind phenomenon at the Vingen fjord adding to the dramatic nature in the area. Photo by T. Lødøen.

The area's archaeological sites and rock art are automatically protected by Norway's Cultural Heritage Act. Since 1980, the central Vingen rock art area and its immediate surroundings have also been part of a strictly regulated 'landscape protection area' established via Norway's Nature Diversity Act. In 2001, further access restrictions were imposed in Vingen through a protection order made in accordance with the Cultural Heritage Act. Automatically protected rock art found outside the protection area at several smaller locations along the Frøysjøen fjord (between the central Vingen area and Hennøya) are also an integral part of the Vingen rock art area.

Adding to the quality and uniqueness of the Vingen rock art, is the location within a much larger pristine landscape that sets Vingen apart from most European rock art areas. This landscape has remained almost unchanged since the rock art production period, 6000-7000 thousand years ago. The area is also famous for the nearby mountain *Hornelen*, whose steep (860 metre) rock face is considered the highest sea cliff in Europe.

Industrial threat to unique rock art in a pristine landscape

On the Dyrstad peninsula, south and west of Vingen, the Municipal Council of Bremanger has recently approved establishment of a stone quarry on the Aksla mountain, 590 masl. The planned industrial area covers almost 2,500,000 m² including a c. 850,000 m² stone quarry from which 130 m³ (360 million tons) of Devonian sandstone will be extracted for European export. The industrial area will host quarry infrastructure, stone crushing facilities and a large shipping port on the northern side of the peninsula. It is located approximately five km west from the central Vingen 'protected landscape area' in close proximity to the smaller rock art sites outside the main area (Lødøen and Mandt 2010; 2012). A stone quarry is already in operation on the adjacent Sætrefjellet mountain, with an established shipping port located on the southern side of the peninsula. See Figures 22-23. Both quarries are operated by the Dutch company Beheersmij Fr. Bontrup BD.

Figure 22. View from Vingenaset towards the Aksla mountain where the quarry and shipping port has been approved. Photo by T. Lødøen.

Figure 23. The Vingen rock art area. A major proportion of the rock art is surrounded by the Vingen landscape protection area. Outside the protected landscape area, rock art has been found at Vingelva, Fura and Hennøystranda (marked with “Rock Art”). Several runic inscriptions and a large Bronze Age cairn are located at the Hennøya island close to the planned shipping port. Image produced by Arkikon AS.

During a protracted planning period, these plans were formally opposed by the Directorate for Cultural Heritage, the County Governor of Vestland, the Norwegian Environment Agency and the Ministry of Climate and Environment. The Directorate for Cultural Heritage maintains that the landscape surrounding Frøysjøen—including the Vingen rock art area and other cultural heritage sites—has significant national and international value. The area provides evidence for the ways in which humans have adapted to the natural environment and resources within it from the Stone Age until the present (see Riksantikvaren 2024).

The landscape is without notable modern interventions. Therefore, its unique qualities remain visible. See Figure 24. There are few such remaining areas anywhere in the world. Therefore, the Directorate for Cultural Heritage opposes the development of Aksla quarry and particularly the shipping port, as they will significantly alter the landscape. Although industrial activity on land will be only partially visible from the Vingen area, based on information provided by the University Museum of Bergen, the Directorate has raised concerns related to the effects of dust and noise pollution from the industrial activities, particularly from the shipping and loading activity in proximity to Vingen. The Directorate has concluded that the landscape and its cultural heritage sites—of which some remain still unexcavated and unrecorded—have intrinsic value linked to knowledge and experience and should be preserved.

Figure 24. Aerial view above the Aksla mountain towards Vingen. The larger landscape around the Vingen area has hardly any modern impact, providing unique opportunity to experience rock art in an impressive and unspoilt landscape setting. Photo by T. Lødøen.

Figure 25. Vingen: The Brattebakken panel to the left. The area has outstanding aesthetic values, represented by the rock art in combination with intentional and meaningful use of the landscape and rock panels. The distribution of the rock art clearly indicates that both the micro and the macro landscape have been integrated in the production of a meaningfully structured iconography. Photo by T. Lødøen.

The County Governor of Vestland has similarly opposed the plans, arguing that they are not in accordance with approved overall area planning and that the impact analysis presented has consistently under-evaluated the negative effects of development (namely, that the shipping port will cause irreparable damage to nature and loss of Red-Listed species). This is supported by the

Norwegian Environment Agency, who have expressed concerns that the shipping port will partly destroy and cause fragmentation of one of the largest concentrations of *Rich boreonemoreal rainforest* in Norway, including the many threatened and Red-Listed species that live there. It will puncture a priceless roadless landscape that currently flows uninterrupted from fjord to mountain, including the exceptional cultural and natural heritage within it. See Figure 25. The Agency also points to the lack of proper evaluation of alternative locations for the shipping port in the planning process.

The Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment supports the viewpoints of the above agencies. It concludes that the plans threaten national environmental interests. The intact landscape surrounding Frøysjøen, its historical and visual qualities, is of natural and cultural significance on a national level. See Figure 26. The planned shipping port and its associated infrastructure will cause severe damage to this threatened natural environment. The Ministry argues that the economic value of quarry development for the Municipality of Bremanger is too small to justify the significant damages that will be caused.

Figure 26. A selection of rock art images from the Brattebakken panel. Photo by T. Løddøen.

Despite a previous decision in 2014 to work towards nominating the Vingen rock art area to the UNESCO World Heritage List, and the opposition during the planning process described above, the Municipal Council of Bremanger has chosen to support industrial development. In accordance with the Planning and Building Act, it therefore falls to the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development to review the case.

The Ministry confirms that it is the shipping port with its related activities and marine traffic that will have the greatest negative effect on both cultural heritage and natural environment at Frøysjøen. However, it is argued that the quarry and shipping port cannot be considered separately. In February 2024, the Ministry finally approved the quarry development on the assumption that the positive economic effects for the local community outweighed the negative effects for the natural and cultural environment.

Should short term economic gain trump unique cultural heritage?

It is clear from the viewpoints expressed by several agencies and institutions that this decision will damage the pristine historic landscape at Frøysjøen both physically and visually. Moreover, industrial activity will bring noise, dust and light contamination. Prevailing winds from the west are known to carry sounds over long distances into the enclosed Vingen rock art area. Visual scarring of the surrounding landscape will bring permanent changes to the area. See Figure 27. Cultural heritage sites in the close vicinity of the planned quarry and shipping port—including several rock art sites, runic inscriptions, gravemounds and a large Bronze age cairn at nearby Hennøya—will also be heavily impacted or destroyed.

Figure 27. Management of rock art at the promontory Vingeneset. The Aksla mountain in the background. Photo by T. Lødøen.

Local, national, and international protests

Since approval of the stone quarry and shipping port by the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development on February 5th 2024, there has been a number of national and international reactions. Amongst those voicing their dismay have been the president of the ICOMOS-CAR scientific committee, the Bradshaw Foundation and other international rock art specialists. The decision and ensuing reactions have received large scale media attention in local newspapers, as well as regional and national media. Lately international sources such as *The Guardian* (UK), RadioFrance (France) and *NRC Handelsblad* (the Netherlands) have also given the case attention. An [ongoing petition](#) has collected more than 5000 signatures since February 8th and is gaining more signatures daily.

Opposition continues

Following approval by the Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development, it has been revealed that the Ministry has based its decision in part on erroneous information regarding environmental values supplied by the Municipality. Questions have been raised in the Norwegian Parliament regarding the quality of knowledge and information on which the conclusion was based. The Ministry has so far failed to provide satisfactory answers to these queries. It has also been pointed out that analyses of environmental consequences associated with the planning process were excluded from the final documents, including those suggesting that the quarry and the shipping port would have a negative impact on the marine environment. Finally, both the Municipality and Ministry have failed to consider the distinction between the Vingen ‘protected landscape area’ and the entire Vingen rock art area when arguing that the distance between Vingen and the shipping port is several kilometres. Rock art belonging to the Vingen tradition has in fact been documented just a few hundred meters from the site of the planned shipping port. Moreover, as mentioned, the potential for further

discoveries in this area is tremendous. This is also emphasised by the fact that previous documentation carried out in the Vingen landscape area between 1998 and 2005 led to the discovery of 700 previously unknown petroglyphs.

Hopefully, as the opposition grows and further knowledge is revealed, there is still time to save the Vingen rock art area and pristine natural landscape from industrialisation and the impact therewith associated. See Figure 28.

Figure 28. International support. A campaign logo developed by the Bradshaw Foundation.

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Project Overview

Grave Goods: Objects and death in Later Prehistoric Britain

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One of the great challenges facing archaeologists is making use of ‘big data’ whilst writing at a scale commensurate with lived human experience. From antiquarian collections to museum assemblages, university-led research projects to the grey literature of developer funded excavations, the sheer volume of material relating to prehistoric burials and funerary rites can be daunting. Yet mortuary archaeology can make vital contributions to both population level analyses as well as moving ‘microhistories’, woven from osteobiographies and object histories. Our project refocused attention on why prehistoric people buried things with the dead. Its title—Grave Goods—was an intentional play on words. These are objects in burials but they are also goods, material culture, that must be taken seriously.

The project, whose full title was ‘Grave goods: objects and death in later prehistoric Britain’, was funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC Grant no. AH/N001664/1) from 2016-2021 and brought together expertise from the universities of Reading (Duncan Garrow), Manchester (Melanie Giles) and the British Museum (Neil Wilkin). Anwen Cooper and Catriona Gibson were the project’s post-doctoral researchers. We started in the galleries of the British Museum, where the project team estimated a total of the 41% of objects on display came from funerary contexts. From the glowing, fragile gold of the Early Bronze Age Mold Cope to the coral adornment of Iron Age shield fittings from Mill Hill Deal, these striking and iconic artefacts often form the centrepiece of exhibitions. Yet case labels seldom do justice to the stories that lie behind them: each one of these funerary objects began with a death; a loss that was dealt with, in part, by the ‘giving up’ of things to the dead. We argue that this is seldom made evident to the visitor. What difference would it make to those labels if we critically considered mortuary materiality: how things were used to mediate death? And what stories could we tell if we focused not just on the large, rare or impressive grave goods (amber and jet necklaces, bronze daggers, iron swords) but the mundane ones (the smoothed pebble, the joint of meat, the pierced shell)? These more idiosyncratic, personal objects were arguably no less important in the performances which negotiated loss. Many of them, such as curious pebbles (categorised in the present as ‘natural’ geological specimens) have simply been thrown away in the past. We thus decided against creating conceptual distinctions between what others have considered ‘true’ grave goods (usually defined as items found on the body or next to it) and wider ‘offerings’ such as food, coverings,

cappings and wrappings (Cooper et al 2019). After all, a coffin is one of the main expenses in a modern burial and can rightfully be considered as an important material offering for the dead. We put it all in.

The project did not have the time nor scope to produce a complete ‘atlas’ of prehistoric burials from the across Britain so we had to be selective: recording only those burials with grave goods within six carefully selected case study regions: Cornwall, Dorset, Kent, East Yorkshire, the Outer Hebrides and Orkney and Gwynedd/Anglesey (Cooper et al. 2022). Some areas are renowned for funerary rites dating to a particular period, others had more representative mortuary evidence spanning our timeframe: the Neolithic to the late Iron Age (c.4000 BC – AD 43). Antiquarian activity has produced wealthy museum assemblages in some counties whereas others have seen more developer-funded archaeology of late. This contrastive set of case studies allowed us to assess aspects of the history of burial archaeology as well as underlying data patterns from the past. The fact that all of these areas contain a section of coastline was not a conscious choice of the team, but it did allow us to investigate connectivity and relationships across both land and sea embodied in some of these grave goods.

Conceptual approaches

In the monograph based on these results (Cooper et al. 2022), we charted the historiography of the concept of grave goods in Britain, exploring ideas which have shaped disciplinary interpretation from the 17th-21st century. The transition from seeing funerary objects as indicators of race, ethnic or culture group during the 1860s-1950s, to models of grave goods as indices of status and power by the 1980s, are well known. Yet we were keen to salvage a more nuanced approach from the pens of antiquarians and early archaeologists, who found the giving up of things to the dead puzzling in an era of burgeoning capitalism and consumption. These early scholars were driven not just by their own material desire but values around inheritance and the bequeathing of their own ‘collections’. We thus used the concept of ‘material affection’ to capture the way in which they sought to understand the ‘devotion’ of things to the dead as a kind of care and respect. We also charted the shift from an interest in the symbolic and semiotic meaning of funerary objects to contemporary models of personhood shaped by theories of symmetrical archaeology and new materialism. (Indeed, this led to a parallel publication which critically considered assemblages that resemble ‘grave goods’ and whether such deposits ‘need’ a body to be considered funerary offerings, critiquing the simplistic concept of the cenotaph—see Cooper et al. 2020). We drew upon both anthropology and folklore to consider practices designed perhaps to comfort, appease or equip the dead, but also protect the living and smooth transformations in new roles or identities they now took on. An attentiveness to performance, ritual breakage and the power of overlooked objects (including those items which imply the agency and afterlife of the deceased; whetstones with blades, strike-a-lights and tinder) helped shape the details we recorded and the conceptual categories we used to describe and organise them.

Big data, big patterns

In total, we collected information about grave goods from 1119 sites, featuring 3129 burials which included 6044 grave goods. The county of Dorset had the most sites, but East Yorkshire stood out for having the largest number of grave goods, and Gwynedd/Anglesey the least. See Figure 29. This data is now [available as a searchable database](#), hosted by the Archaeology Data Service. It can be searched by site name, site type or location, or by object type or material. The results can be downloaded as a

useable database for personal analysis with distribution maps. Wherever possible, links to the current location of the artefacts are provided as well as other sources of information.

Figure 29. Location of sites with grave goods plotted against background ‘heat map’ of all known burial sites recorded within the relevant HER for the six case study regions within the UK.

The Grave Goods project demonstrates convincingly that there is no direct correlation between what we traditionally see as defining ‘technological’ thresholds and mortuary materials; copper and bronze were evident in Early Bronze Age burials, but this material was most common in the Iron Age, with iron itself a rarity. The latter usually occurred as part of composite objects from the Middle Iron Age onwards. Lithics are common throughout all periods, with tools such as spindle whorls and quernstones, as well as ‘natural’ or geological specimens forming an important part of the Early-Middle Bronze Age and Middle Iron Age funerary assemblages, complementing worked stone tools in earlier burials. Yet pottery was the most common grave good of all, defying any simple correlation between the three major ‘ages’ and the materials used to craft grave goods. Through a finer-grained study of Bronze Age Dorset and Kent, we were also able to selectively examine mortuary material

culture against what we have termed the ‘wider material repertoire’ of daily life; highlighting the importance of context and issues such as the ‘missing majority’ of the world of organics.

The scale of this data enabled us to depict in graphic form a new, evidence-based understanding of changes in grave goods and burial practice over the long-term. See Figure 30. The Neolithic period was both practically and conceptually difficult to characterise. In many cases, the objects associated with human remains (in chambered tombs, long barrows and other comparable site) were no longer associated with distinct individuals due to frequent re-ordering and sorting of those remains; perhaps they never had been, and were simply generic offerings to the dead, sometimes brought much later to these sites to be dedicated to the community of ancestors. The increase in both the prevalence of burial (cremation and inhumation) and the number of objects interred in such graves during the Early Bronze Age around 2000 BC was very clear. Yet over time, the quantity of objects in burials dwindled, so that by c. 1200 BC the most common type of grave good was a single pot. We know from the wider material repertoire that this was not due to period of material impoverishment; the period of the Middle to Late Bronze Age (c. 1500-800 BC) saw huge quantities of metalwork deposited in hoards. Evidently, this material was not thought to be socially or conceptually appropriate for the dead; mortuary practice had changed.

Figure 30. Figure 2 Top 50 objects in graves through time (darker shading indicates greater numbers of objects; maximum value for each object type per 100-year time slice (summed probability) is shown on the right-hand side.

We were also able to highlight the strong regionality of grave goods. Had we chosen different case study areas, the Middle-Late Iron Age might have been represented by only a few examples of grave goods, given the patchy and often short-lived traditions of both inhumation and cremation over the first millennium BC in the UK. Yet the selection of East Yorkshire, Dorset and Kent enabled us to interrogate fascinating intersectional associations of people and things, during this period. The dramatic peak just prior to Roman conquest is also particularly visible, where a wide variety of objects in graves could be observed in regions in close contact with both Gaul and the wider Roman Empire. Throughout the study we have thus tried to situate these trends with wider research on population mobility (arising from both aDNA and isotope studies) and socio-political or historical processes and events.

Themes and issues

Having presented the major chronological patterns and ‘big data’ results, we eschewed a period-based approach for a more thematic structure for the remainder of the study (available as an open access download from [Oxbow Books](#)). We explored understated objects in graves, giving attention to animals (as food offerings and companions as well as potent materials), pebbles and stones layers and both isolated objects or small assemblages, sets or bundles. We discussed the fact that whilst the meaning of some of these items will escape us, we can instead evoke the intention behind the gathering together of a group or collection of things that were meaningful to the deceased or their mourners. We gave attention to the most common grave good – the pot – ranging from its use for food offerings to vessels for the dead, feasting repertoires for the wake or afterlife, to aesthetic objects in their own right. Through different case studies we considered the way this object often spoke of wider affiliations in form, design and temper.

Two complementary chapters explored the ways in which grave goods allow us to explore both time and movement. By examining the distance that both raw materials and types of objects travelled, we were able to examine the character and extent of material networks in prehistory, noting that these did not necessarily coincide with population mobility. ‘Things’ have the potential to travel further than people through hand-to-hand or down-the-line gifting or trade. We mapped the distant ‘exotic’ through all of our case study areas, noting unsurprising peaks of exchange in both the Early Bronze Age and the Middle-Late Iron Age. Yet we cautioned against seeing this as a representative record of material mobility as a whole, given that other exotic, long-distance objects were on different depositional trajectories and ended up not in graves but other contexts. We also noticed a particular fascination with what we termed the ‘local exotic’; substances and objects that came from neighbouring regions to the burials, perhaps embodying the personal connections of the deceased or commemorating rare but meaningful journeys undertaken within their lifetime. Other materials were intensely local; quartz in Early Bronze Age Cornwall, sandstone in Middle Bronze Age Dorset and chalk in Iron Age East Yorkshire. These we situated within the everyday lives and meanings of materials close to hand, furnishing the dead with the familiar. Moments when the dead were commemorated in terms of extensive material relations were thus contrasted with those where intensive relations were given greater prominence in the grave.

In our chapter on temporality, we considered different temporal rhythms that grave goods allow us to explore, from evidence of protracted rites to single moments in time. We explored the ‘multi-temporal’ material culture of Neolithic tombs, where acts of reorganisation and sorting resulted in grave goods losing their individual associations: moving across time into different arenas of meaning.

Figure 31. A reconstruction of the Folkton child burial. © Craig Williams.

Figure 32. The Folkton Drums. ©Rose Ferraby.

We contrasted what is often unproblematically taken as the ‘ideal’ inhumation of the Early Bronze Age (with burial quickly following death) to increasing evidence for protracted rites which incorporate curated and fragmentary remains. We also explored this phenomenon in relation to cremations where the final interment might gather together generations of the dead and their cremated artefacts, sometimes stacked in order, others commingled. Pyre goods received special attention, contrasting objects that went up in flames with those added later as another means of extending mortuary time. We also observed an ontological contrast between the fragmenting of people and the coherence of things in some of our time periods. Meanwhile, Late Iron Age cremations from Kent evoked a greater obsession with the present, with grave goods drawn from a swiftly changing material repertoire: deploying new ceramics, bronze and silverware or Roman style trappings, to convey power and personhood *à la mode*.

Conclusion

Alongside the monograph (Cooper et al. 2022) and two research papers, the project led to a temporary exhibition at the British Museum, the text of which can be read here: [Death, Memory and Meaning: on the trail of Grave Goods](#), taking us back to the stories which inspired the project. We also produced a [Schools Resource pack](#), including some wonderful visualisations by artist Craig Williams (Figure 31), Rose Ferraby (Figure 32), Kelvin Wilson and Chie Kutsuwada, and a set of moving poems by Michael Rosen, which you can listen to on his [YouTube channel](#). In sum, we hope we have left a rich legacy not

just of new analysis, concepts and ideas, but compelling stories of the role of grave goods, to inspire the next generation of archaeologists.

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Research Overview

The Early Copper Age mould found in the Baffoni Cave (AN): looking back and forward. Multidisciplinary analysis, research and replicas of an object found 70 years ago

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An early Copper Age mould was found during excavations led by Antonio Mario Radmilli in 1952 and 1954 in the Grotta dei Baffoni (Baffoni Cave) (Radmilli 1953, 1956). The site is beside the Frasassi Gorge, near Genga (province of Ancona in the Marche region) in east central Italy (Montanari *et al.* 2022). It is not only the only Copper Age mould found in Italy to our knowledge, but also counts among one of the few examples that have ever been found (Pignocchi *et al.* 2021; Fiorentini 2023; Pignocchi, Fiorentini, Montanari in press). See Figure 33.

Figure 33. The Copper Age marl mould from the Baffoni Cave with the virtual 3D stamp of the hollow. Photo by Romina Nespeca of the Department of Construction, Civil Engineering and Architecture of the Università Politecnica delle Marche in Ancona, by permission of SABAP AN-PU.

The Frasassi Gorge is a spectacular canyon formed by the Sentino River through the core of the Calcare Massiccio reliefs (Monte Frasassi-Monte Valmontagnana). The gorge is world famous for its marvellous natural caves, such as the Grotta Grande del Vento (The Great Wind Cave), one of the most beautiful karst caves of Europe. The Baffoni Cave (in which the mould was found) lies 65 m above the Sentino River on the opposite side of the gorge and has a single 12 x 40 m chamber oriented southeast from its south-facing entrance. See Figures 34-35.

The Radmilli excavations

Research inside Baffoni Cave began in 1951 following discovery reports of archaeological artefacts from the Speleological Group of the Marche to the Superintendence for the Antiquities of the Marche region. Superintendent Giovanni Annibaldi appointed Gilberto Piangatelli (who was not an archaeologist) to carry out a series of surveys and shallow sample-taking within the cave.

Unfortunately, no archaeological specimens remain from these early investigations. In 1952, Annibaldi called upon Antonio Mario Radmilli (who was then working at the Luigi Pigorini Prehistoric Museum in Rome) to carry out scientific excavations in the cave (Radmilli 1953). Radmilli continued the excavations started by Piangatelli, digging two large trenches on the N-NW side of the cave, the first close to the entrance and the second 15 meters inside. The excavations were undertaken with the help of Radmilli's wife Aurora De Carolis and Delia Lollini from the Superintendence for the Antiquities of the Marche region.

The excavation near the entrance, which reached a depth of about 4 m was sterile until 3 m, where Radmilli found some Upper Pleistocene cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*) and other wild animal remains, such as mountain goat (*Capra ibex*) and hare (*Lepus europeus*). At a depth of 3.40 m, Radmilli encountered a horizon of soft, fine-grained, yellowish sediment containing limestone rubble and pieces of speleothems along with an avian long bone from a bird and more cave bear remains. The second trench showed an archaeological sequence. The layers were removed in spits to the depth of 3.0 meters. These were partially identified by Radmilli, who initially divided them generically between the Roman Age, Iron Age, and Bronze Age.

In all, the excavation was completed in just seven days. In 1954, Radmilli returned to the Frasassi Gorge to continue the previous excavations. Unfortunately, the original journal recording that excavation campaign is now missing. The only information that can be obtained is from Radmilli's paper (Radmilli 1956). In short, he continued the stratigraphic exploration by widening trench B and continuing in depth to about -4.60 m.

At that time, Radmilli modified the previous interpretation of the deposits in the cave thanks to the correlation with the investigations carried out at the same time by Salvatore Maria Puglisi at nearby Grotta del Mezzogiorno (Midday Cave). Still, Radmilli kept the excavation method unchanged. His stratigraphy remained based on artificial cuts and distinguishing only three periods: the Roman Age (from 0 to -1.10 m), the Iron Age (from -1.10 to -1.70 m) and, indistinctly, levels of the Bronze Age (from -1.70 to -2.30 m). As for the lower levels (from -2.30 to -2.80 m) previously attributed to the Early Bronze Age, he recognized that some specimens found there could be compared with specimens of

the Copper Age or the late Neolithic Ripoli culture also found in the lower layer of the Grotta del Mezzogiorno.

Figure 34. Location of Grotta dei Baffoni (Baffoni Cave) in the Frasassi Gorge (Genga – province of Ancona – Marche region). Map from Google Earth and edited by the authors.

Figure 35. The entrance of Baffoni Cave. Photo by Gaia Pignocchi.

Figure 36. Close up of the tiny green metal spherules on the surface of the mould's hollow. Photo by Gaia Pignocchi, by permission of SABAP AN-PU.

The mould (Figure 33), which was later shown to have contained copper residues (Figure 36), came to light during the 1954 excavation. It was found in the lower cuts (from 2.30 to 2.80 m) associated with coarse pottery but without any more precise stratigraphic position. The cut where the object was found is not numbered. We know only that it came from the lower units where human and animal bones were also found. Some of that material was recently dated between 3640 and 3380 cal. BC; that is to the mid-fourth millennium BC (Early Copper Age) (Montanari *et al.* 2022).

The object

The artefact, already identified by Radmilli (1956, 528; Figure 3.7) as “a clay mould for casting... containing a fragment of copper” has been curated by the National Archaeological Museum of the Marche in Ancona for 70 years. Despite its uniqueness, the mould was not subjected to any specific or detailed study until now.

The mould measures max 12.2x8.5x7.0 cm and resembles an irregular, beige-coloured parallelepiped. It was modelled by hand and has a central hollow measuring max 4.6x3.2x1.6 cm, which was probably formed by pressing a thumb into wet clay. The surface of the hollow is dark gray. One out of two original suspension holes survived, showing traces of wear due to the sliding of a small rope. See Figure 33. A small green metal sphere (c. 3 mm) is also visible in the mould's surface, as are four tiny metal spherules, each less than one millimetre in diameter. See Figure 36.

The mould is irregularly broken lengthwise. Part of the edge that formed the perimeter of the cavity is missing. The margins of the fracture of the clay block are abraded, and the clay inside is a darker colour.

Considering the function as originally hypothesized by Radmilli, it was clear to us that the object would have to be a single matrix for casting, given the convexity of its upper surface (which would have prevented any alignment with a second specular matrix). At this point, both the traces of blackening inside the hollow and the presence of the metal spheres support its plausibility as a mould.

What is more difficult to understand is what kind of metal object(s) might be obtained from such a mould. Thanks to the *corpus* of Italian Copper Age axes (Carancini 2023), it was possible to identify the type of axe to the Pila or Patrica type (Carancini 2023, 70-72, nn. 67-70). See Figure 37.

Figure 37. Pila and Patrica type axes and drawing of the Baffoni mould (Carancini 2023, modified).

These are very small, squat axes found in Umbria and Lazio. They are almost miniature versions of subtrapezoidal axes from the early phase of the Copper Age. They fit well with the radiocarbon dates obtained on the bones, and also suggest second third of the fourth millennium cal. BC, i.e., Early Copper Age.

The analysis

Contrary to what was previously thought, the mould matrix is not made of terracotta. Rather, it is of a sedimentary rock with a carbonate-marl compound containing planktonic foraminifera as well as a lower percentage of silicate microcrystals. Mineralogical-petrographic analyses of the marl were carried out in the Applied Petrography Studio of Orestina Francioni, GeoPT Studio (Camerano-AN). Specialized observation by Rodolfo Coccioni of the University of Urbino led to the identification, among the various planktonic foraminifera, of the *Trilobatus praeimmaturus* (Aquitanian-Langhian)

and to the absence of the typical spherical forms referable to the genus *Orbulina* that appeared only in the Langhian. This suggests that the original marl formation dates to the Early Miocene.

Marl found in the Marche region has a calcareous composition (between 70-90%), which is not suitable for modelling, since it fractures while drying. The contrary occurs with marl from the Schlier Formation, which we took from a stratigraphic section near Gubbio, on the west side of the Umbria-Marche Apennine. Having a higher clay content, the marl from this formation can be easily modelled with the addition of modest quantities of water and does not crack during drying.

Further analysis by X-ray microfluorescence spectroscopy (μ XRF) of the elements present in the different layers of a sample of the Baffoni marl mould revealed an average of 60% of CaO and 27% of SiO₂, which are values compatible with the marl formation taken near Gubbio. This analysis was carried out by Pim Kaskes (Chicxulub K-Pg Impact Project, Vrije Universiteit Brussel).

Other analyses were directed at the mineralogical composition of one of the metal droplets. Marcello Cabibbo (Università Politecnica delle Marche in Ancona) found that the spheres have a very high copper content (max. 92%) with a high percentage of zinc (8-12%) and smaller percentages of silver (0.5%). These findings led us to assume that the mould could also have been used to refine copper from a tennantite-tetrahedrite mineral, such as Fahlerz. This kind of copper ore can be found in the Apuan Alps and in the Metalliferous Hills in Tuscany.

Kaskes also carried out additional analysis of a sample of the mould by micro-XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence) mapping using SEM-BSE images that revealed a high concentration of Cu and Zn on an outer portion of the mould. Lithic analysis showed that the mould was only heated to about 400°C, much lower than expected for a mould required to sustain thermal shocks.

The replicas

The work on the Baffoni Cave mould's replicas began in late 2020 (Pignocchi et al. 2021; Fiorentini 2023). As we originally presumed the object was made of clay, a first experimental project was carried out. The objective was to recreate multiple clay moulds and pour molten copper into them to see which kinds of metal objects could be obtained. It was decided to make four moulds: MF-1 was made using soil from a field, MF-2 using commercial red clay and MF-3 and MF-4 using commercial white clay imported from Tuscany. These moulds were modelled by hand. Like the original, the hollows were made by pressing a thumb on the wet clay, trying to reach the exact measurements of the original. Despite the care taken during this operation, the hollows' dimensions varied from specimen to specimen. Only one of them had the exact dimensions of the original, that is a length of 4.6 cm, width of 3.2 cm wide and a depth of 1.6 cm.

The experimental moulds were left to dry thoroughly before being fired on a manual forge using commercial charcoal, in an attempt to replicate a Copper Age open pit oven. During this experiment, mould MF-4 broke and mould MF-3 vitrified in a manner that prevented further use. The firing of the remaining moulds and of a crucible was successful. The highest temperature recorded temperature was 1,114 °C and the average was 465.31 °C for MF-1 and 755.5 °C for MF-2 by a laser thermoscope (model Axiomet AX-7540, set to record a maximum of 1.150 °C) during this process.

MF-1 and MF-2 were used for ten castings, five per mould using an electric furnace. The process affected the moulds and the surfaces of their hollows. MF-2's hollow proved to be less durable than MF-1's. MF-2 broke in multiple places, which made it nearly unusable after just five castings. On the other hand, MF-1 showed little signs of wear, suggesting that it could be used for additional castings.

There was also a change in the colours within the hollows. Since the internal walls darkened more and more as the castings took place, the colour of the original specimen was eventually reached. Lastly, during the pouring process, some boiling was recorded, with drops of molten metal spreading on the moulds' surface. Once cooled, these droplets were very similar to the ones seen on the original.

After the mineralogical-petrographic analysis, Montanari found that the same kind of marl can be found near Gubbio in Umbria: the so-called Schlier blocks. He kindly provided us with some examples of this marl from Gubbio (Umbria) and some of another marl type from the village of Apiro, in the region of Marche so that we might test these different materials. Due to variations in clay content, we decided to employ both marls to recreate as many moulds as possible.

To reproduce the hollow precisely, we enlisted the collaboration of Paolo Clini and Romina Nespeca (Department of Construction, Civil Engineering and Architecture of the Università Politecnica delle Marche in Ancona). They created a 3D model of the original mould and a cast of the hollow itself. This was used as a further support in recreation of exact replicas of the hollow, along with two pieces of modelling clay (brand DAS) that Pignocchi pressed into the original hollow. See Figure 38.

Figure 38. The hollow on replica MF MAV-2 was made by pushing a metal stamp on the wet surface of the mould. The stamp itself was made by pushing a DAS model taken from the specimen on a mould replica, and then by filling the hollow with molten lead (photo by Mauro Fiorentini).

Figure 39. One of the three copper castings for which MF MAV-2 has been used. The forge is a simple fire pit which on previous experiments proved capable to reach over 1.538° C by using a single bellows and hardwood coal. Photo by Mauro Fiorentini.

Figure 40. MF MAV-2's hollow after three castings. Many tiny copper prills can be seen, some stuck on the mould's surface, just like those on the specimen. The hollow's surface darkened and reached a colour similar to the specimen. The mould made of marl proved to be much more resistant to thermal shocks than the moulds made of clay, despite the fact it was not even properly fired. Photo by Mauro Fiorentini.

Fiorentini first made two moulds using the Apiro marl formed of tiny greyish stones (similar to limestone) that were pulverized with a rock into table salt-like fragments. The Apiro marl moulds began to crack while drying. The marl from Gubbio was naturally pulverised already to a consistency similar to flour. A single mould of Gubbio marl was used for three successful castings. See Figure 39. The Gubbio marl mould proved to be much stronger and easier to work with than the other moulds used for casting (Fiorentini 2023). As said, tiny drops like the ones on the specimen could be seen on the mould's surface and in the hollow. The hollow itself showed a change of colour and its surface has been darkened by the contact with the molten metal, showing dark-green marks that can be compared to those on the original. See Figure 40.

We believe that the results of our experimental investigations into this unique object support Radmilli's initial interpretation: that the object was indeed used as a mould for copper casting!

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Exhibition Review

‘Soundmarks: York’- by Rose Ferraby and Rob St. John: A Review

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Soundmarks: York is free to visit, 10-3pm, at: Dig, St. Saviourgate, YO1 8NN (UK) until July 31st and online for the [exhibition narrative](#) or the [audio soundscape](#).

The project

York Archaeology’s ‘DIG’ centre in the north of Britain is usually a bustling hive of excited children, learning about the ancient past and how to explore it through imaginative hands-on experiences and enthusiastic archaeological guides. Yet if you visit it over the next few months, you will find a small, inspiring room off the main nave of this re-used church, washed with sound, light and colour. [Soundmarks: York](#) is the culmination of a collaboration between artist and archaeologist [Rose Ferraby](#) and artist, musician and filmmaker [Rob St. John](#).

Part of the AHRC funded [Roman York Beneath the Streets Project](#) (AH/V015338/1) led by Martin Millet (University of Cambridge) and John Creighton (Reading University) in partnership with York Archaeology, York Museums Trust and the University of Ghent, the exhibition conjures the ‘hidden’ Roman archaeology of a city more famous for its Anglian and Viking discoveries and the rich timber-framed and stone-built heritage of its Medieval city. The research project upon which it is based uses cutting-edge Ground Penetrating Radar survey to map the underground extent of *Eboracum*, an important Roman urban centre of the north, which at one point included both a military fort and a *colonia*. A rich history of antiquarian collecting, extensive rescue and developer-funded excavations and a network of extraordinary archives and museum collections will enable the project to re-envision the city where Septimus Severus died, and where Constantine was proclaimed Emperor. As the Yorkshire Museum’s exhibitions evidence, this was a thriving Roman settlement where different peoples met, traded, worked, lived and died: leaving behind an extraordinary legacy through which we can examine their identity, beliefs, tastes and aspirations.

To conjure that hidden history for a wider public audience, Rose and Rob have developed a trail which takes the visitor from the ‘arrival’ point of York’s iconic station and major Roman cemeteries, up over the river into the city, past the sites of the Roman Multangular tower and through its medieval walls, into the fort and back out to the riverside wharves and settlements that sprawled across the banks of the Ouse. Downloadable as an easily navigated [art trail map](#), you can also listen live to the audio narrative or download each waystation’s track which combine exquisite poetic narrative with musical soundscape: all of which are available online through the website (<https://roseferraby.com/portfolio/soundmarks-york/>). Yet if possible, I would encourage you to visit DIG in person, to view the beautiful, site-specific, painted

collages and the film which accompany each of the waystations, rich with insights into York's upstanding and buried remains, flanked by cases of iconic finds from York Archaeology's Hungate dig.

Figure 41. The Railway Station (from Soundmarks: York). © Rose Ferraby

A unique collaboration

Rose and Rob's work will be familiar to anyone who visited *The World of Stonehenge* exhibition at the British Museum in 2022, through a soundscape and artwork inspired by [Seahenge](#). This subtle installation was so effective at transporting visitors to the saltmarsh in which this wracked timber monument was set, with its upturned root-bole and circle of crusted bark uprights, that some visitors swore they could 'smell' the sea! Their use of on-site sounds, blended with digital recordings from tape that had been immersed in water or buried in the ground created a unique audio experience that somehow captured the passage of time: flitting between past and present. Another collaboration of theirs, [Soundmarks: Aldborough](#) built on many years of fieldwork by Rose Ferraby and Martin Millett at this Roman town in North Yorkshire, to create a walking tour around the modern village, bringing to light aspects of both the ancient and historic landscape.

Waystations

The first stopping point of *Soundmarks: York* is accompanied by a metallic threnody that conjures the hum of the **Railway Station** (Figure 41) and the journeys and arrivals of different groups from across the Empire who made *Eboracum* their home. Rose's painting conveys the towering girder arcs of this sweeping architectural junction built on a curve; a gigantic rib cage enclosing the elongate plots of inhumation cemeteries that once lay beneath its tracks. Some of these burials preserved delicate textile imprints in the gypsum that infilled some of the coffins, alongside beautiful items of jet and bronze. The call of gulls and geese draw the visitor onto the next collage, **River**, a glorious, pulsing swirl of high summer blue sky, framing the hulls and sails of boats, plying their trade along the River Ouse (Figure 42). Beneath its surface, Rose's abstract forms convey a tangle of silt and weeds, eddies of water hiding collapsed quays, lost cargoes of amphorae and silver bellied fish. The soundscape evokes the river as a conduit not just of goods but beliefs: 'grand narratives and small stories washed ashore, caught in the eddies of history'. The river laps the edge of Rose's next painting, **Museum Gardens**, as the soundscape enables the listener to replace the upstanding medieval ruins of St Mary's Abbey with the pale gold stonework of the fort walls, its narrative evoking silhouettes of guards with their standards, backlit against a red sun. Outside the bulging bulwark of the Multangular tower, edgeland settlements and middens gave up innumerable fragments of the past lives that now fill the cases in the Yorkshire Museum set within the garden grounds.

The next waystation is **Minster**, its medieval edifice rising up from the foundations of the original Roman fort. It is hard to appreciate the subtle topography of this rather flat and built-up city, but the soundscape evokes the way a rise in the ground was monopolised by military occupation, becoming the keystone in their march north and west. Famous names—Hadrian, Severus and Constantine—and significant moments in history seep into the stone here. Rose's accompanying collage switches from elevation to plan view: evoking both the medieval frame of the minster's nave as well as the regimented order of roads and barrock blocks: 'streets percussed by marching feet'. The soundscape is threaded through by the sound of pipes and horns, ornamenting a description of the visual power of the legions whose ghosts are still supposedly glimpsed in certain parts of the city. Look closely at the painting and you will see forms that evoke the 'colour and sheen of their uniform... cavalry, decorated with loops and fittings'... linked tegulae from Roman armour, horse-gear, belts and buckles.

Figure 42. The River (from Soundmarks: York). © Rose Ferraby

At **Dig** itself, the river reappears in both soundscape and collage; its curves beset with small industry, the ‘lurking odours of forging and firing’ and riverside landings, the chink of rigging, flap of sails and bump of hulls moored up along the Ouse. The rhythmic sound of hammer and shunt of baskets and boxes sets the tone for this busy stopping point, but it gradually morphs into a more sombre tone, evoking how rising floodwaters deposited the living so that ‘the dead moved in’. The narrative captures how larger patterns of weather and water infiltrate and swamp the ingenuity of the city’s builders and engineers. Yet from the cemeteries that replaced them came some of the most beautiful recent grave goods to emerge from the city: jet bangles, beads and segmented bracelets, iridescent glass vessels and burnished pots imbued with the patina of individual lives. Step outside the gallery and you will see a selection of these beautiful artefacts from Hungate displayed in the flanking glass cases.

Finally, at **Micklegate**, the clang of carts and chink of bells evoke the busy hubbub of the civilian settlement, with its shops and markets and influx of people and stock. The cleansing warmth of the bath house, the solemnity of its temples and bustle of its stalls are conjured by blending modern street chatter with a low refrain. Rose’s collage for this final waystation seems to capture the ‘steam, smoke and smells’ of these Roman streets crammed with small archways, courtyards and cart-rilled tracks. Stacked rust red tiles, paving and tesserae, column bases, lintels and keystones evoke the spectacular buildings which must have awed those used to the constraints of timber, wattle and daub. This busiest area of the city broils under a murky sun. Yet at the close of this soundscape, birdsong draws the listener to voyage out of this city along its roads, north to the Wolds or west to the Vale and beyond.

Creative legacies

In a small space, this immersive bricolage manages to conjure much of the Roman history of York. The project beautifully evidences how creative responses can form a moving and meaningful bridge between our specialist reports, monographs and displays for the visiting public. It requires a longer stint in other (quieter?) venues but enhances the extraordinary hub of museums, historic buildings and sites which make this city a beacon of heritage practice and research. As part of the *Roman York Beneath the Streets Project* this way of ‘seeing’ such hidden history thus complements other visualisation techniques, such as reconstructed 3D digital cityscapes. As valuable as they are, such models can be prescriptive and date quickly. Rose and Rob’s more imaginative response is rich and joyous: arguably helping archaeologists themselves see the creative power of their own work in a new light.

Like the best of archaeological exhibitions, *Soundmarks: York* also includes two cases that record the ‘making’ (or should I say, ‘excavation’) of both painted collage and soundscape. One glass case contains the snipped and discarded fragments of Rose’s collages, physical sketchbooks of ideas and images of her gallery workspace. See Figure 43. The other explains how Rob’s audio-recordings were made, including the insertion of hydrophones into the murky flood-waters of the Ouse and the recording of its rain-spattered streets. See Figure 44. Here is the materiality of making alongside the finished thing, reminding us to attend to practice and process, as an integral part of any archaeological endeavour. The glow of these collages and [their accompanying soundtrack](#) haunted me long after I had left, etched as they are with both the flow of modern life and the audio patina of decay and decomposition. Visit if you can; listen in, if you cannot.

Figure 43. Soundmarks in the making—assemblage collage fragments.

Figure 44. Recording York's Soundmarks audio archaeology.

Conference Report

4th VCWAP Roundtable “Work-Life Balance in and After Academia”

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The 4th [Virtual Conference for early-career Women Archaeologists and Paleontologists](#) (VCWAP) was held from 6th to 8th March 2024. VCWAP is an online meeting organised by the [Association of early-career Women Archaeologists and Paleontologists](#) (AWAP). Thanks to the financial support of several international research institutions (TRACES UMR 5608 of the Université Toulouse Jean-Jaurès & CNRS, PALEVOPRIM UMR 7262 of the Université of Poitiers & CNRS, Subsilience of EVOADAPTA, Universidad de Cantabria, IPHES-CERCA’s Maria de Maeztu Unit of Excellence and Transmitting Science), free registration was provided to both speakers and attendees, allowing them to access a wide range of research presentations and complementary events.

The scientific programme included 41 oral presentations and 33 posters, organised into 5 themed sessions. In accordance with previous editions, the 4th VCWAP featured a virtual gallery where 13 palaeoartists presented their work. The Scientific Committee awarded three prizes: First and second place for oral presentations as well as a prize for the best poster. A final prize for the best paleoart was selected by the conference attendees.

Alongside the scientific events, a workshop and a roundtable discussion were held on topics common to young female researchers regardless of their professional stage. The roundtable was dedicated to “Work-life balance in and after academia”. The expression “work-life balance” can have different meanings depending on factors such as geographic location, cultural identity, life stage and a person’s immediate environment (Brough et al., 2020; Gragnano et al., 2020). During the two-and-a-half-hour roundtable (Figure 45), we discussed what “work-life balance” meant to attendees, how to achieve equilibrium for mental health and productivity and how to navigate between personal needs and work expectations. To ensure a plurality of perspectives and experiences for the roundtable, we invited three researchers at different stages of their academic journey: 1) An early-career academic with a non-permanent position at a predoctoral or early postdoctoral stage (Nit Cano), 2) An academic with a permanent position representing tenure track position or established researchers with a permanent contract (Dr. Susana Carvalho) and 3) a researcher who left academia after going through the postdoctoral process and is now working in industry/with policy-makers (Dr. Eve Boyle).

Whilst academic inquiry allows us to investigate the world around us and to further our knowledge of a variety of topics, participating in academia itself is becoming increasingly more demanding, particularly for those who identify as women or genders other than cis-male (Domingo et al., 2022). Researchers must navigate between project development and active research, writing academic papers and grants, public engagement, teaching, mentoring duties and administrative roles amongst multiple other commitments. The increasing demands of academia, thus, have a high likelihood of disrupting an individual’s work-life balance. This can be particularly prevalent for women and those who identify as genders beyond cis-male, as these individuals often find themselves—through choice or delegation—more frequently taking on additional service and/or caring roles (Guarino and Borden, 2017; Domingo et al., 2022; Nicholls et al., 2022). It should also be noted that other minority groups within academia—such as people of colour, with disabilities, and/or belonging to the LGBTQI+ community—face further disturbance to their work-life balance due to the prejudices to which they are subjected (Dupree and Boykin, 2021). One of the starting points for gender equality is to openly discuss the social constructs and academic expectations of women’s roles.

Figure 45. Screenshot of 4th VCWAP Roundtable participants.

The 4th VCWAP roundtable yielded fruitful discussion and questions for further contemplation. After the conference, we sent an online conference evaluation survey to all conference participants to follow up on the work-life balance roundtable. The survey questions were based on poll questions launched during the roundtable and particular talking points from the discussion. All questions had multiple-choice answers. A total of 70 people responded to the survey; the number of respondents for those questions specific to the roundtable ranged between 55-67. The majority of the respondents were aged between 20-34 years (75.6%) and in the early career stage (undergraduate, masters, PhD and postdoctoral researchers, 63.2%). Most (91.4%) identified as women, 5.7% identified as men and

2.9% identified as non-binary. Almost all respondents (94.3%), were archaeologists (57.1%) or paleontologists (31.4%), with the remainder working in both fields or other closely related scientific fields.

The participants were asked what work-life balance means to them. Almost half (46.3%) of respondents stated that work-life balance means being able to manage deadlines and personal life. Some (16.7%) answered that it represents work-schedule flexibility. A minority (7.5%) answered that it implies working only for those hours that are specified in the contract. When directly asked, 71% of respondents said that they worked more hours than specified in their contract.

Subsequent questions then asked the participants if they think their institutions are taking care of their mental health and whether they have ever suffered from burnout. Only one out of five (21.2%) respondents said that they think that their institution cares about their mental health. 78.1% of respondents said they were suffering from or had experienced burnout during their careers.

Respondents were asked to state whether they considered the academic environment 'Highly demanding' (41.5% of respondents), 'Overall competitive' (53% of respondents), 'Healthy' (3.1% of respondents), or 'None of the above' (1.5% of respondents). When asked if they had ever had issues setting boundaries with work/work requests/colleagues or bosses, almost two-thirds (63.5%) of respondents answered in the affirmative.

Only 16.4% of respondents said that the conferences they attended provided childcare services. When asked if and how many additional roles they take on beyond their study/job description (e.g., running student groups, organising department events, various committees, etc.,) the majority of respondents (80.4%) stated that they have between 1- 4 'extra' roles.

To conclude the survey, we asked participants if they had seen a change in attitude towards work-life balance since they started their studies/jobs. A little under half the respondents (43.6%) stated that things had improved a little, 10.9% said that it had improved a lot, but 28% answered that things were the same or had become worse.

The results of this survey highlight several important points regarding work-life balance in academia. Many people are consistently working beyond their allocated working hours. However, at this point we cannot state whether this is due to enjoyment of their work or the amount of work an individual must do. In addition to the roles outlined in their job description, we found that people often (80.4% of respondents) took on multiple additional roles. Numerous additional roles are likely time-consuming and, thus, may impact the number of extra hours that one finds oneself working. Future studies should investigate time allocations to different roles within and beyond an individual's job description.

High rates of burnout and issues setting boundaries with work and/or colleagues alongside the perceived lack of mental health support from institutions is another worrying trend. Thus, we urge institutions to invest in mental health resources for their employees and students and to make them available and accessible to all those who need them. However, the topic of mental health is still associated with stigma (Nicholls et al., 2022), which may discourage those who need the resources from accessing them. As a community, academia needs to work on providing a more supportive environment in which all can participate at their best capacity.

Whilst facilities such as childcare are beginning to be provided at conferences, it still is a rare occurrence. We hope that the continued inclusion of childcare facilities at future conferences will increase inclusivity and allow a broader demographic to share and discuss their research at these events. The impact of easier access to affordable childcare should also be considered beyond

conference events. The demands of an academic schedule can cause difficulties for childcare alongside the conventional hours of nurseries, preschools, and schools.

Respondents found the academic environment to be highly demanding and generally competitive (94.5% of respondents combined). Given the rigorous nature of academic research and the need to require appropriate funding for research to support students and trainees (amongst other things!), this may not be surprising. However, in terms of work-life balance, just over half (54.5%) of respondents said that they saw some improvement in attitudes towards work-life balance since the start of their studies/careers. Thus, whilst some facets of academia and work-life balance may currently seem bleak, there is still hope. As a community, we have the power to instil changes in the types of roles undertaken and their expected workloads. Those changes will have lasting, positive effects on work-life balance, so that we may continue to explore the topics that interest us in a healthy environment.

Acknowledgements:

We would like to thank all the 4th VCWAP organisers and the AWAP for making this conference possible. Finally, we would like to thank everyone who took the time to answer the survey and allowed us to gather these results.

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Conference Report

Solid Sterling Science Communication: Current Archaeology LIVE!

Samantha S. Reiter

TEA Editor

What do Neanderthal DNA, a cutting-edge archaeological site identification initiative, the Stone Table from C.S. Lewis' *Chronicles of Narnia* and cosmetic company Lush's 'Geo-FIZZ' all have in common? That would be *Current Archaeology LIVE! 2024*, the one-day conference organized by British popular archaeology magazine *Current Archaeology*. I recently had the pleasure of attending *Current Archaeology LIVE!* for the first time just a few weeks ago (24th February), and I cannot recommend it enough. Not only were the topics thrilling—Matt Pope's review of the presence of Neanderthals in the Channel Islands and Kevin MacDonald's *tour de force* of Mali and Senegalese tumuli were particular high points for me in this regard—but all of the speakers were top notch. The organization by Carly Hilts and the *CA* editorial team were also impeccable. The All-Star line-up delivered an excellent helping of science liberally seasoned with a palpable hint of dry British humour. In short, *Current Archaeology LIVE! 2024* represented the very best kind of science communication: informative *and* entertaining. The day left the audience with both food for thought and a hunger for more!

The Conference

The conference started with a bang. UCL's own Matt Pope gave a sensational rip-round of the current state of knowledge and recent developments regarding the presence of Neanderthals on the Channel Islands (specifically at La Cotte de St. Brélade, Jersey). He did a masterful job of tying together diverse body of European evidence, including everything from butchered animal remains and game drives to aDNA. He spoke poetically of 'travels in lost landscapes' and put the potential new information to be gained from the 12 teeth discovered at La Cotte de St. Brélade into perspective delivering eye-opening insights into the current paradigm regarding Neanderthal/ *Homo sapiens* relations via what he called a "spectrum of being human".

Next followed a joint presentation by Ali Cameron (Cameron Archaeology) and Alice Jaspers (University of Southampton) which discussed the fascinating discovery a missing monastery by means of examining a medieval manuscript known as the Book of Deer. The two speakers worked very well together, spinning their research discoveries into a sort of docu-drama, and peppering their talk with vivid textural details (from the importance of site cake to knocking on doors for permission to dig in people's gardens) and seemingly contradictory questions like "how many calves went into [the vellum for] the Book of Deer?". An overview of their research will be featured in a future issue of TEA, so watch this space!

A talk by Nathalie Cohen of the National Trust covered the multi-period site of Smallhythe, located along the border of Kent and Sussex. Her talk covered everything from the fact that late Victorian English actress Dame Ellen Terry had purchased Smallhythe as a country retreat in her later years to the over 10,000 metal findspots in the surrounding fields. Cohen showed schematics of the ‘mud docks’ which remained from the work of early shipwrights in the nearby waterways as well as the Samian Ware and one Mercury figurine from the 4-5 buildings of a nearby Roman settlement.

Ashley Tuck of Wessex Archaeology spoke on the excavation of the Hornsea Project One Cable Route in the marshes of northern Lincolnshire. Poetically calling the work “Between the Salt Water and the Sea Strand”. The area of investigation included a late Iron Age enclosed settlement with a few roundhouses with some Iron Age, Roman, Anglo-Saxon and medieval materials as well. The high water table at the site posed challenges not only to modern archaeology, but also to the early people who made their lives there. Nevertheless, said Tuck, the evidence they gathered surprisingly pointed towards a closed subsistence economy in the area: sheep and cattle were pastured in the wetlands, horses and cattle were used for traction (and then eaten at the end of their lives). Tuck finished his presentation with an excellent ‘cliffhanger’ by mentioning evidence for the presence of sand-washing on site (a medieval means of salt production).

From Lincolnshire, our attention moved much further afield: to west Africa. Kevin MacDonald (UCL) gave what was (for me) an absolutely mind-blowing examination of “Tumuli through time” in Mali and Sénégal, which were constructed slightly later than prehistoric mounds in Europe. He began by speaking of early archaeological and amateur excavations in the early 1900s and then moved forward in time up to more recent archaeological work. Some of what original archaeologists had claimed were ‘mounds’ seem—after more recent investigations—to actually be tells. However, MacDonald also spoke about actual tumuli fields and gave some quite intriguing ethnographic insights about the sacred landscape known as the Dô, which contained local religious kings and the subsequent burials grouped around them.

The original plan for the final slot of the second session (Natasha Billson of Behind the Trowel) fell through due to illness. However, Julian Richards (of Meet the Ancestors fame) jumped into the breach to deliver a talk spanning his 50+ year career in archaeology, entitled on “My Career in Ruins”. He told self-deprecating stories (e.g., when a former headmaster remarked “I hope Richards finds something useful to do with his life, but I doubt it”), thrilled us with the joy of his first archaeological discovery (a brass key at the bottom of a medieval cess pit) and nimbly illustrated lessons learned from working with children (when building models of Stonehenge, work with vegetables rather than biscuits!).

After lunch, Julian Thomas (University of Manchester) spoke about recent investigations at the so-called ‘Arthur’s Stone’, a Neolithic chambered tomb in Herefordshire that was the original inspiration for C. S. Lewis’ Stone Table in the Chronicles of Narnia. Thomas compared his work on the site with others further afield in Europe before cleverly spinning a picture of Arthur’s Stone and its surroundings as a significant location to which materials were brought from great distances. He painted a picture of a complex landscape that may—or may not—have had competing monuments within it.

The subsequent speaker, Maiya Pina-Dacier of DigVentures, galvanized the audience with her figures from DeepTime, an archaeologist-guided AI and citizen science initiative for the identification of archaeological sites via satellite imagery and LiDAR. In short, the first ‘round’ of DeepTime identified 4,500 previously unknown sites in less than three months! But interestingly, until further notice and after several subsequent campaigns, it seems that people are still better at identifying sites than an AI. As Pina-Dacier pointed out, searching for sites in this fashion “connects people who love archaeology with opportunities to do archaeology”. It also suggests that, reassuringly, in the competition of archaeologists vs. robots, archaeologists are still in the lead.

The penultimate speaker was Rachel Frame of the Vindolanda Trust, who presented about excavations at Milecastle 46. Similar to Cameron and Jaspar’s presentation, Frame spoke about the discovery of new finds as well as the recent results of new work in a forthright and conversational manner which was both elucidating and entertaining. A crucial result of the recent work showed shifts of the pH of the soil in relation to rainfall. This is important as it highlights the high variability of the soils at this heritage site and underscores that this will have a negative effect on the preservation of any organic materials which have yet to be uncovered.

Last in the conference lineup came John Gater of *Time Team*/SUMO GeoSurveys, who took the stage and opened his keynote by saying “I’d like to apologize in advance for any swear words.” He then proceeded to give one of the most touching, nostalgic, fascinating (and hilariously funny!) keynotes I have ever attended. Gater’s hour-long review discussed the challenges *Time Team* met over the years building the public image of archaeology (and geophysics of course!) from the ground up. He was also visibly delighted to report that *Time Team* has risen from the ashes of its previous position on the UK’s Channel 4, like the proverbial phoenix. Although it is missing some of the now departed though still much-loved original characters, it is nevertheless producing new adventures which go directly to their own dedicated [channel on YouTube](#).

Gater talked about pranks by the *Time Team* team, such as being essentially name checked by cosmetics company Lush (GeoFIZZ/‘geophys’). He also spoke earnestly about the satisfaction of working with veterans in Operation Nightingale, of which he said “working with these veterans was a privilege. It put things into perspective,” before adding with his characteristic humour “I mean... the thing about working with the military... look at how straight the trenches are! The spoil heaps were immaculate!”

The Awards

Gater’s wonderful keynote, alternating between touching reflections and razor-sharp hilarity was followed by the presentation of *Current Archaeology*’s annual awards. The awards are chosen entirely by public vote for the most outstanding contributions to archaeology in the following categories: book, rescue project, research project and archaeologist. For a first timer like myself, it felt a bit like I would imagine the archaeology equivalent of the Oscars. I also have it on good authority (from the CA Editorial Board itself) that nominees are *not* informed ahead of time whether they will be awarded or not, so everything happened... well, quite appropriately, given the title of the conference: LIVE! This year’s award candidates were:

Book of the year:

Picts: Scourge of Rome, Rulers of the North by Gordon Noble and Nicholas Evans¹

The Rise and Decline of Druce Farm Roman Villa (60-650 CE): Excavations 2012-2018
by Lilian Ladle

Winters in the World: A Journey through the Anglo-Saxon Year by Eleanor Parker
and

WINNER *Doggerland: Lost World under the North Sea* by Luc Amkreutz and Sasja von der Vaart-Verschoof (eds)

Rescue Project of the year:

Pitch perfect: tackling a previously unknown Roman villa at Dings Crusaders RFC, Cotswold Archaeology

Excavating Weeley Barracks: Echoes of the Napoleonic Wars in Essex, Oxford Archaeology

Harpole's Hidden Gem: Excavating Early Medieval Britain's most Significant Female Burial, MOLA

WINNER *The Knowe of Swandro: Excavating Eroding archaeology in Orkney, Swandro-Orkney Coastal Archaeology Trust/ Bradford University*

The Gloucester: Piecing Together the Story of a Royal Wreck, The Gloucester Project

Research Project of the year:

WINNER *The Ness of Brodgar: Marking 20 Years of Neolithic Discoveries, Ness of Brodgar Trust*

Pondering Penywyrlod: In Search of the Early Origins of the Cotswold-Severn Long Cairn and Barrow Group, William Britness (Clwyd-Powys Archaeological Trust) and Alisdair Whittle (Cardiff University)

At the Edge of the World: Exploring Early Medieval Asceticism on the Skelligs, John Crowley and John Sheehan (Cork University Press)

Rural Romanitas: Rethinking the Role of Villas, Martin Henig (University of Oxford), Grahame Soffe, Kate Adcock and Anthony King (Association for Roman Archaeology)

The Bare Bones: Presenting a Very Regional Neolithic, Matt Ritchie (Forestry and Land Scotland)

¹ Also shortlisted for the EAA Book Prize

Archaeology on Prescription: Using Fieldwork to Support York's Mental Health Provision, York Archaeology

"Tired beyond all telling": Revealing the Hard, often Brief Lives of Pauper Apprentices, Durham University, University of York and Washburn Heritage Centre

A Monumental Mystery: Unpicking the Evolution of Arthur's Stone, The Arthur's Stone Project

Archaeologist of the year:

Andrew Birley (Director of Excavations on Hadrian's Wall)

WINNER Nick Card (Ness of Brodgar)

Amanda Clarke (Associate Professor of Field Archaeology, University of Reading)

The day was just fading into that unique grey of London evening when I stepped out of the UCL building with 500 other attendees of *Current Archaeology LIVE! 2024*. For me, it was the first bright day of the year, and I had just spent it indoors—and I could not have regretted it less! *Current Archaeology LIVE! 2024* was a class act and exhibited engaging science communication from start to finish. I can't wait to see what they do next year!

Community Spotlight

Community on Fortification Research (COMFORT)

Timo Ibsen, Giacomo Fontana, Anna K. Loy, Sebastian Messal and Tanja Schreiber

Community Board Members

Of the numerous cultural monuments from prehistory and history, fortifications are undoubtedly among the most fascinating manifestations of material evidence of a widespread, multi-faceted and long-term cultural phenomenon. Fortifications emerged for the first time about 10,000 years ago and have existed ever since. They are called by many names, such as (but not limited to): castle, fort, fortress, stronghold, rampart, citadel, bulwark, enclosure, oppida, promontory fort, or hillfort—all of which mean fortified sites of various types. Because of their omnipresence, fortifications continue to be important elements of natural and cultural landscapes even today, often constituting part of our cultural identity as reflected in folklore, poetry, prose and the arts.

Due to their size, complexity and heterogeneity, fortified sites are usually difficult to examine as a whole and, therefore, are still not understood in depth. Despite the long research history on fortifications (which goes back to the early days of archaeology itself!) surprisingly little is known about general development trends and there still remain many questions about definitions, terminology, chronology, typology, functions and the role and interconnection of fortifications within the wider cultural landscape.

The archaeologists of today use a whole range of new powerful investigation methods beside excavations: geophysics, aerial photography, LIDAR scanning, pollen analysis, drilling, geochemical soil analysis, microstratigraphy, C14-dating, dendrochronology and GIS-based studies to display, combine and holistically analyse all the various data. As highly visible and usually relatively well-preserved monuments that can be visited and experienced by people, fortification also attract great interest from sectors outside archaeology, such as tourism, educational institutions, the construction sector and urban planning.

Figure 46. The 60 COMFORT members in 2023 by country. Graph by T. Ibsen

For tackling these issues and to improve the understanding of fortifications, the Community on Fortification Research (COMFORT) was established in 2018 within the framework of the EAA. The Community is managed by a board, which currently comprises five members: Sebastian Messal, Tanja Schreiber, Anna K. Loy, Giacomo Fontana and Timo Ibsen, all from different European scientific institutions. In 2023 COMFORT had 60 subscribed EAA members from 24 different countries. See Figure 46.

COMFORT's main aim is to connect researchers who work with the investigation, research and management of fortifications. Furthermore, it seeks to create a worldwide and interdisciplinary network for fortified sites (including archaeology, history natural sciences, cultural heritage management etc.). Since there is no common strategy for the investigation of fortifications, the identification/clarification of research issues and the implementation of joint investigation strategies forms COMFORT's third main task.

As the interest in fortifications and their interdependencies between phenomena like conflict, hierarchy, or trade, as well as their impact on the social and spatial organization constantly grows, it becomes difficult to keep track of the almost uncountable number of related archaeological activities and affiliated publications. Hence, there is a necessity of exchanging knowledge on a worldwide level. Against this background COMFORT wants to offer a discussion and exchange platform for interested researchers and stakeholders of other disciplines and sectors and aims at exchanging fortification related knowledge on a pan-European level by means of the following objectives:

- Offering a discussion platform and enlarging the network of fortification researchers
- Encouraging the study and exchange of information relating to fortification research
- Identifying current research issues
- Implementing joint investigation strategies
- Developing common documentation standards
- Contributing to the development of frameworks to interpret fortifications
- Promoting the EAA among archaeologists who study fortifications
- Organising and coordinating sessions dedicated to the archaeology of fortifications and related structures at EAA Annual Meetings, particularly including sessions of general interest allowing for wide participation
- Fostering cross-European networks and collaborations

- Supporting early career researchers within fortification research

COMFORT's objectives are discussed during the sessions and meetings at the annual EEA-conferences, as well as through specialised workshops and online events. Some of the sessions and workshops are published. One such example is the first international COMFORT workshop, entitled "The setting of fortifications in the natural and cultural landscape", which took place on 5 and 6 March 2020 in Schleswig at the Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology (ZBSA). A total of 25 archaeologists from Germany, Russia, Norway and Finland took part in the workshop, which was financially supported by the ZBSA and the Department of Archaeology and Cultural History at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).

On 29 August 2020, the community also organised a session at the EAA's virtual annual conference entitled "Just a demonstration of Power? The setting of strongholds within their landscape [COMFORT]" (session # 448). Both events resulted in the publication *Fortifications in their Natural and Cultural Landscape. From Controlling Space to the Creation of Power* (Schriften des Museums für Archäologie Schloss Gottorf, Ergänzungsreihe, Band 15; Bonn 2022), edited by T. Ibsen, K. Ilves, B. Maixner, S. Messal, J. Schneeweiß. The volume included a total of 16 English articles presenting case studies to demonstrate the full range of possible functions depending on the respective situation of a fortification in the natural and cultural landscape. The articles further discussed possible differences and similarities in different geographical regions in order to explore the underlying mechanisms for site selection.

The publication of another session at the EAA's 2021 AM in Kiel (virtual) "Towards an international archaeology of fortifications: methodologies and interpretations" (session #273) included a total of 26 English oral contributions by archaeologists from various European countries is in preparation and will probably be published in 2024 within the ROOTS study series (Cluster of Excellence ROOTS, Christian Albrecht University Kiel; editors: Jens Schneeweiß, Ariane Ballmer and Timo Ibsen). It contains 17 articles on European fortifications which present new excavation results, discuss their construction and shape and interpret both single strongholds as well as whole regions in terms of the fortifications found within them.

Since 2022, COMFORT has been organising online lectures, offering scientists and interested laypeople a varied programme for getting to know various fortifications and projects, as well as a forum for those who want to bring a relevant topic to the public themselves. COMFORT is also institutionally anchored at the Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology (ZBSA) as part of the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) in Schleswig, northern Germany (<https://zbsa.eu/fortification-research-comfort/>). In contexts in which it is appropriate for events and announcements to be made more widely, it also maintains a presence on [Facebook](#) and [Twitter](#).

Community Integrating the Management of Archaeological Heritage and Tourism

Sofia Fonseca and Ben Thomas
Community Co-Chairs

The [Community Integrating the Management of Archaeological Heritage and Tourism](#) was established as a result of discussions at the round table “ArchaeoTourism on the Move: Developing Guidelines for Europe” held at the EAA Annual Meeting in Glasgow in September 2015. Participants in the roundtable wanted to continue the discussion on archaeological tourism beyond the conference. Initially formed as a Working Party, in 2018, it evolved into an EAA Community. The Community took a more comprehensive approach to the topic of archaeological tourism—one that was not focused solely on developing guidelines. This transformation facilitated engagement with a variety of themes, including ones that were pertinent to the host countries of EAA meetings and propelled forward the dialogue on sustainable management and public engagement within archaeological tourism. See Figure 47.

Figure 47. Pula amphitheatre, Croatia: one of the most visited archaeological sites in the city of Pula.
©Sofia Fonseca.

Since its formation, the Community has been active in organizing sessions, round tables and discussions, addressing a wide range of topics from sustainable heritage tourism to the challenges posed by mass tourism and the impact of COVID-19. The Community has also discussed how we—archaeologists and heritage professionals alike—communicate with the public. These gatherings have fostered international collaboration and contributed to the ongoing discourse on sustainable archaeological heritage management.

Furthermore, the Community has made significant strides in international networking and policy advising, collaborating with organizations like UNESCO, ICOMOS and various tourism and heritage

entities. This network has supported efforts to review and develop guidelines and charters, such as the ICOMOS International Cultural Tourism Charter.

Publications and conferences have been key outlets for disseminating the work and research of Community members, contributing to the broader understanding and development of strategies for managing archaeological heritage in tourism. Efforts have been made to create Working Groups within the Community that focus on critical areas for consideration:

- 1. Developing European Guidelines for Archaeological Tourism:** The group's primary objective is to craft comprehensive guidelines that serve as a blueprint for managing archaeological tourism across Europe, ensuring it is sustainable, respectful and enriching for both visitors and the heritage sites.
- 2. Accessibility at Archaeological Sites:** In addition, we aim to make archaeological sites more accessible to diverse audiences, ensuring that everyone has the opportunity to experience and learn from our shared heritage.
- 3. Communication in Archaeology:** The Community also focusses on enhancing how archaeological findings and knowledge are communicated to the public, making the past more engaging and understandable for all.
- 4. Climate Change and Its Impacts on Archaeological Sites:** Finally, we also address the pressing issue of how changing climates affect our archaeological sites and heritage and develop strategies for mitigation and preservation.

These Working Groups reflect the Community's commitment to advancing the field and addressing contemporary challenges.

We invite you to visit our [website](#) and join us and our network of experts from around the world. See Figure 48.

Figure 48. Image of the Community on Archaeology and Tourism members database, which can be consulted at our [website](#) ©EAA Community on Archaeology and Tourism.

Announcements

Photojournalism Competition

Are you *TEA*'s next photojournalist of the year?

Submit one image (photo or drawing) in **portrait*** format alongside a max 400-word text and find out!

Ranging from archaeology's early roots in cabinets of curiosities and the enthusiasm of Victorian antiquarians to the latest advances in GPR, molecular science and heritage practices, it is no secret that archaeology is a wide and varied discipline. We look at everything from rock art and pigments to isotopes, the experience of moving through the landscape and the values of contemporary communities. Is the study of the past a science, an art form or a social science? Various arguments support all of these options, but what do *you* think? Once again, *TEA* welcomes submissions to our photojournalism competition. We seek images that illustrate the great depth and breadth of archaeology and which include short answer essays on the following theme:

ARCHAEOLOGY: ART OR SCIENCE?

We have all been there—some excavators can turn a planum into a masterpiece while themselves completely covered in mud. Others work with pipettes, petri dishes and column chemistry whilst clad in pristine lab coats. Both are archaeology, and that is what we are after! Show us through pictures and text the joy and beauty in the art or science of *your* branch of archaeology!

How to enter:

Submissions should be made by email to tea@e-a-a.org by **1 August 2024 at 23:59 CET**. Each entry should include a single high-resolution (600 DPI) portrait-style image (.tif or .png) with an accompanying text (max 400 words).

The text should describe the subject matter of the photo, its location, archaeological relevance and a few lines relating it to archaeology as art or science (or both!). The text should be a .word file, and should also include a thumbnail of the image described. In your email text, please state your full name,

institution (if you wish it to be posted) as well as your EAA membership number. Please include 'TEA Photojournalism competition 2024' in the subject line of the email.

By submitting an image to the competition, you confirm that you have or have obtained copyright permission, that you provide permission for *TEA* to print the image in question as a cover, should your entry be among the winners and you also extend permission to the EAA to use the image with accreditation in its promotional materials.

What you can win:

The three winning entries will have their EAA membership fees waived for 2025 and will receive certificates describing them as "TEA Photojournalist of the Year 2025". The images will feature on the winter, spring and summer issues of *TEA*, and will be announced as *TEA*'s Photojournalists of 2025.

Rules of the competition:

You must be a current EAA Member to enter.

Each Member may submit only one entry, so choose wisely.

You may only submit an image on your own behalf.

The image must be oriented in portrait to potentially fit the cover of a future *TEA* issue.

You must have copyright permission for the image and you must agree to provide permission to *TEA* to reprint the image. This includes the possibility of the image being included in a future issue of *TEA* spotlighting the entries of the competition.

All subject material which answers the competition theme will be considered, though it must also be appropriate to being a cover of *TEA*.

Judging criteria:

After closing date, all submissions will be evaluated by a panel (including both professional photographers as well as archaeologists). Those short-listed will be notified by end of August that their entry has been selected for the second round of the evaluation process, which will be by popular vote by Members of the EAA. Before the voting begins, shortlisted entries will be spotlighted on EAA's social media channels alongside their texts before the final vote. Winners will be notified by end of October.

***Please note that images which are not in portrait orientation will not be accepted. If you have an image that you would like to contribute that is square or in landscape format you must crop it to portrait format before sending it in to the competition.**

In Memorium

Chris Tilley

1955-2024

Michael Rowlands

UCL

Chris was very proud of the contribution his work made to creating a new intellectual synthesis between anthropology and archaeology. His first position at UCL was as a joint post in Archaeology and Anthropology. There he founded a joint undergraduate degree that is now the most successful Undergraduate degree in Archaeology at UCL.

His approach to Material Culture was to treat it as an intellectual synthesis that whilst originating in the intellectual history of Anthropology/ Archaeology; it was not subsumed by them. Instead, as a joint founder of the *Journal of Material Culture*, he emphasised the undisciplined value of Material Culture that would by virtue of its very materiality escape the constraints of any particular disciplinary history and have much wider philosophical impact.

His own particular approach was to pursue this through developing the idea of landscape; his book *A Phenomenology of Landscape* is widely recognised as a major contribution to our interpretation of human experience. The study of landscape, both in archaeology and anthropology and more widely has been revolutionised by the approach he advocated in this volume. His book *The Materiality of Stone* is another seminal work which explores how the treatment of rocks and stone were deeply meaningful to people who inhabited and used them. It can be applied as an approach to understanding both prehistoric and contemporary material worlds.

There was never any end to his intellectual drive and desire to pursue new approaches to the understanding of material culture as a unifying philosophy. My last visit to him in hospital ended with him asking me to get some books from the UCL library which I dutifully had waiting to take down to him. It is with great sorrow that whilst what we talked about may not be realised, we can take some solace in the contributions and human inspiration that Chris and his work has contributed to so many.

Kristian Kristiansen

Gothenburg University

Mike Rowlands informed me last night of the sad news that Chris Tilley had died after long illness; what a terrible loss for archaeology, as well as for his family. I agree with what Mike wrote; he still had much to give. However, let us remember all that he gave to archaeology.

He was the great theoretical renewer and interpreter who never stood still and who moved from structural Marxism to phenomenology—a nearly impossible journey! He was a restless intellectual who always came up with something new and interesting. He was not bothered by theoretical contradictions. Instead, he explored them, as shown by his collaboration with Michael Shanks which resulted in the *Black and the Red* books.

I remember inspired discussions with him in our younger days at the Humanities Centre. In the late 1980s he resided in Copenhagen for several months at a time during which he had no job (before Lampeter and UCL). Some of us tried to point out that one could not be both be a Marxist and a postprocessualist. But it was to no avail! Truth be told, archaeology benefitted from that. His legacy will live on.